

Technical file and coding-book for the appended dataset

Deliverable 7.1

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List of abbreviations

Conceptual/analytical terms	Definition
CAWI	Computer-Assisted Web Interviewing
CI	Confidence Interval
DK	Don't know
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GPP	Gender Positional Deprivation
HDI	Human Development Index
NUTS	Nomenclature of Units for Territorial Statistics
PTV	Propensity to vote
RD	Relative Deprivation
RWPP	Right-Wing Populist Party
WP	Work Package
Countries	
DK	Denmark
DE	Germany
UK	United Kingdom
ES	Spain
HU	Hungary
CH	Switzerland
Surveys/organisations	
CIS	Centro Investigaciones Sociológicas (Centre for Sociological Research)
DNES	Danish National Election Study
EES	European Election Study
ESS	European Social Survey
GESIS	Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences
ISSP	International Social Survey Programme
MOSAICH	Measurement and Observation of Social Attitudes in Switzerland
UN	United Nations

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Executive summary

This report is the first deliverable outcome of Work Package 7 (WP7) of the UNTWIST project. The aim of WP7 is to conduct the survey administration, data harmonization and clean-up of the final database. The survey measures at the public opinion level all the different dimensions of gender-based needs and demands and put them in relation to voting behaviour. In this sense, it is a key piece to test the UNTWIST hypothesis of whether RWPPs (Right-Wing Populist Parties) act as challenger parties, representing specific gender-related needs, demands and fears of citizens “on the margins” previously neglected or ignored by mainstream parties. In this report, we focus on the final outcome of the main tasks carried out before, during and after the survey fieldwork, which is the final appended database, providing an in-depth description of how the data was produced. This report is divided in five sections: Section 1 provides the technical documentation and fieldwork description; Section 2 describes the variable harmonization strategy; Section 3 outlines the weighting procedure; Section 4 presents the annotated description of the appended database version and, lastly, Section 5 provides the unified database codebook.

Introduction

This report is the first deliverable outcome of Work Package 7 (WP7) of the UNTWIST Project. The aim of WP7 is to conduct the survey administration, data harmonization and clean-up of the final database. It also builds on the final survey master questionnaire from WP6. The survey is a key piece to test our hypothesis that those who experience gendered positional deprivation are more likely to vote for Right-Wing Populist Parties (RWPP) than those who do not. Gendered positional deprivation (GPP) is the theoretical elaboration of the concept of “feminism's losers,” which is central to the UNTWIST project.

Experiencing gendered positional deprivation has the following implications: 1) the relative deprivation experienced by citizens with an explicit gendered group-based identity, which causes them to feel resentment; 2) the substantive set of different needs, demands and concerns relevant to each gender-based identity, in relation to which they think their group is relatively disadvantaged; 3) the identification of women in general, subgroups of women in particular, feminism, feminist women, feminist movements, etc. or any other body promoting feminism, as the key outgroup for relational and longitudinal comparison, relative to which relative deprivation is experienced. These three meanings overlap, while those who experience the third level may see themselves as “feminism's losers” (Ruiz Jiménez et al., 2023).

The survey makes a valuable contribution to the UNTWIST project by measuring at the public opinion level all the different dimensions of gender needs-and-demands and put them in relation to voting behaviour, trying to give a robust empirical answer to the question whether RWPP act as challenger parties, representing specific gender-related needs, demands and fears of citizens “on the margins” previously neglected or ignored by mainstream parties.

Main tasks on this work package were developed in a three-fold way. First, decisions were made regarding subcontracting, sampling and administration of the questionnaire. The second step consisted of administering the questionnaire, compiling the data, harmonizing and cleaning-up of the database. Lastly, the final task consisted of appending survey data with country data. In this report, we focus on the final outcome of this process which is the final appended database, providing an in-depth description of how the data was produced.

The report addressed three main objectives:

- (1) Provide a summary of the survey technical information and highlight the key aspects of the fieldwork, which are relevant to understand how the collection of data has been out in practice.
- (2) Describe the weighing procedure that was followed after the data collection ended to ensure the maximum quality of representativeness of the target population.
- (3) Describe the post-fieldwork adjustments conducted to obtain the final outcome, such as harmonization of key variables, appending of country data and preparation of a unified codebook for the final database.

This report is structured as follows. First, we provide the overview of the technical documentation and a detailed description of the fieldwork stages (Section 1). Next, the harmonization process of key variables is outlined (Section 2). The third section is devoted to develop the weighting strategy (Section 3). Finally, we present the annotated description of the appended database version (Section 4) and the unified UNTWIST Survey Codebook (Section 5).

1. TECHNICAL DOCUMENTATION AND DESCRIPTION OF THE FIELDWORK

Before starting the fieldwork, it was necessary to make a set of decisions regarding the technical specifications of the survey. This involved defining the universe and scope of the survey, choosing the data collection modality, and mainly, crafting the sample design to ensure the statistical representativeness of the population universe. In addition, decisions were also made about the design of the RWPP women voters' over representation. Once these criteria were established, the fieldwork began, which was divided into three stages: pilot study, main and boost. The technical specifications of both samples (main+boost), as well as the different implementation stages are described below:

1.1 Universe, scope, mode of collection and accessibility

- **Universe:** All citizens persons aged 18 and over, in the countries as listed in the "Geographical Unit".
- **Time period:** 21/10/2024 (beginning of main field) - 09/01/2025
- **Geographical unit:** Denmark (DK), Germany (DE), Hungary (HU), Spain (ES), Switzerland (CH) and United Kingdom¹ (UK).
- **Data type:** Numeric
- **Mode of collection:** Data collection was carried out using the online interview technique (*Computer-Assisted Web Interviewing - CAWI*), applied in two modalities: probabilistic panels and conventional or commercial panels.
- **Data collector:** VERIAN
- **Data accessibility:** All the technical documentation and survey data are openly available on Zenodo with the following persistent identifier - DOI (10.5281/zenodo.15083114). The database is available in CSV, SAV and DTA; is accompanied by the documentation included in this Deliverable and the relevant metadata, complying with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). The microdata file will be embargoed for one year, until March 31, 2026.

1.2 Sampling design

¹ This geographical unit is limited to Great Britain, as the survey did not include Northern Ireland. However, in order to facilitate comparability with other international cross-country surveys and databases, we keep the denomination 'UK'.

A probabilistic panel was deemed the most appropriate basis for the survey to test the proposed hypotheses and theoretical expectations. This approach makes it possible to infer, at the population level, the behavior observed in a representative sample of the populations studied, thus guaranteeing the validity and robustness of the results obtained.

Therefore, the decision was made to carry out the main study exclusively with probability panels. This allowed for 100% probability sampling in the six countries under analysis. However, as will be detailed later in this report, it was necessary to resort to a non-probabilistic panel in Denmark in order to achieve the objectives set. Nevertheless, the maximum population representativeness of the data obtained was assured.

In addition, in order to achieve the oversample (Boost), non-probability sampling was employed, using a single non-probability panel for all countries. This technique was necessary since by using a probability panel in the main field, the target sample, although representative, was limited in terms of volume. The natural drop (inflow) of interviews within this segment of interest was not enough to accomplish the initial sampling and subsequent analysis needs.

In order to design a probability sample that reflected the societal composition of each country, VERIAN carried out a socio-demographic analysis of the structure of the probability panels in each of the countries participating in the study. Based on this analysis, they proceeded to perform an implicit stratification by sex and age group. Within these bands, educational level was also considered as a classification criterion. In order to maximize the representativeness of the sample, an additional classification was made to ensure greater geographic dispersion, using the analysis of the NUTS (*Nomenclature of Units for Territorial Statistics*) territorial units of each country.

Table 1.2.1 Distribution by sex and age stratification

	UK	Denmark	Hungary	Spain	Germany	Switzerland
Men	50%	51%	52%	51%	49%	51%
Women	50%	49%	48%	49%	51%	49%
18-24	14%	15%	12%	12%	12%	12%
25-39	24%	23%	22%	20%	22%	24%

40-54	23%	22%	28%	28%	22%	25%
55-64	15%	16%	14%	16%	18%	16%
65+	24%	24%	24%	23%	26%	23%
Tertiary education (university and higher)	31%	43%	30%	41%	33%	46%

Source: Own elaboration based on Verian Fieldwork Report.

Table 1.2.2 Geographic distribution

Country	Level	Name
Denmark	NUTS 2	Regions
Hungary	NUTS 2	Planning regions and statistics
Spain	NUTS 2	Autonomous Communities
Germany	NUTS 1	Government regions
UK	NUTS 1	Government regions
Switzerland	NUTS 2	Cantons

Source: Own elaboration based on Verian Fieldwork Report.

The distribution of the theoretical sample, therefore, was drawn as follows:

Table 1.2.3 Distribution of the original sample + boost

Country	Pilot	Initial sampling	Presence without forcing RWPPs voters*	Boosted sample (boost) RWPP voters (Estimate)
United Kingdom	100	1.750	47 men +47 women	203 men +203 women
Germany	100	1.750	34 women	216 women
Denmark	100	1.000	19 women	231 women
Switzerland	100	1.000	58 women	192 women
Hungary	100	1.000	77 women	173 women
Spain	100	1.750	47 women	103 women
Total	100	8.250	329	1.321 women

* The number of RWPP voters that naturally responded in the survey in the main sample.

Source: Own elaboration based on Verian Fieldwork Report.

After extracting the sample, a pilot study (pre-test) was launched by means of a soft launch of 100 interviews per country, in order to verify that the script worked correctly. This soft launch was not implemented simultaneously in all countries to mitigate the risk of widespread incidents in the event of failures. For this reason, it was decided to start the process in the country with the largest sample, which had also been the reference country in the creation of the questionnaire: United Kingdom. At the conclusion of the pre-test, a detailed analysis of the sampling distribution obtained in the pilot was carried out to evaluate how the panel had performed and to make the necessary adjustments for the main field. The results of this analysis were as follows:

Table 1.2.4 Distribution by sex, age and education after the pilot

	UK	Denmark	Hungary	Spain	Germany	Switzerland
Men	43%	48%	44%	46%	56%	66%
Women	57%	52%	56%	54%	44%	34%
18-24	9%	4%	4%	0%	3%	3%
25-39	22%	22%	32%	4%	25%	12%
40-54	31%	23%	38%	28%	34%	26%
55-64	20%	13%	12%	36%	25%	25%
65+	18%	38%	15%	32%	15%	34%
Tertiary education (university and higher)	36%	45%	30%	42%	51%	54%

Source: Own elaboration based on Verian Fieldwork Report.

After visualizing the results and verifying that in certain cases there was a significant deviation, VERIAN proceeded to distribute the sample in 5 batches crossed by age range. For these purposes, a 'Batch' is defined as a group of items processed or managed together in a single operation cycle, in this case, a set of panelists receiving the survey simultaneously or in a given period of time. In this way, it was possible to launch the necessary sample at each precise moment, thus avoiding sampling errors or overrepresentation. Initially, Batch 1 was launched in each country, and once all the panelists in that batch had responded to the survey or, alternatively, had ignored the contact attempts made through various channels, the next batch was launched.

This approach ensured a representative sample of each country's society, without distorting the results due to bias in the selection of participants. It also allowed more accurate control over the data collection process, optimizing the quality of the information and reducing the possibility of errors in the representation of the different demographic characteristics. This ensured more consistent and valid results for subsequent analysis.

Table 1.2.5 Example of Batch crossed by age range

Batch		1	2	3	4	5
Age	18-24	238	238	237	237	238
	25-39	466	465	465	465	465
	40-54	643	644	645	643	643
	55-64	377	377	376	377	377
	65+	561	561	562	562	561
Total		2.285	2.285	2.285	2.284	2.284

Source: Own elaboration based on Verian Fieldwork Report.

1.3 Boost of Right-Wing Populist Parties voters

Specialized studies, backed on robust empirical evidence, have highlighted that populist radical right political actors have played an important role in mobilizing and normalizing gender conservatism particularly among men (Spierings & Zaslove, 2017; Anduiza & Rico, 2022). The following table shows the percentage of men and women that have voted for the main RWPP of each country in the last election. In general, the percentage of male RWPP voters is higher than female voters, with the exception of the UK, where the vote share is noticeably low for both men and women voters.

Table 1.3.1 Vote recall percenting for the main RWPP

Country	English party name	Vote recall (total)	Vote recall (women)	Vote recall (men)	Source
Germany	Alternative for Germany	5,27	1,56	3,7	GESIS 2022
Denmark	Danish People's Party	8,7	7,2	7,6	DNES 2019
	The New Right	2,4	1,4	2,7	
Spain	Vox	7,5	4,9	10,4	CIS 2023
Hungary	Fidesz	54,84	20,60	34,24	ESS10 (2020-2022)
UK	Brexit Party/Reform UK	0,36	0,24	0,12	
	United Kingdom Independence Party	0,24	0	0,24	
Switzerland	Swiss People's Party	23,28	9,96	13,32	

Source: own elaboration based on ESS,2020-2022; GESIS,2022; DNES, 2019; CIS, 2023.

Relling on this data and the existing literature, we decided to oversample a target group of 250 women voters of right-wing populist parties (RWPPs) in the six countries, and 250 men in the case of the UK. To reach the oversample we use the propensity to vote question (Q5), which is a question of general vote intention given a party list: *“We have a number of parties in [COUNTRY], each of which would like to get your vote. How likely is it that you will ever vote for the following parties? Please answer on a scale where 0 means “not at all likely” and 10 means “very likely”.* Respondents selected for the oversample were those users responding that would vote for a RWPP with a likelihood between 8 and 10. The RWPP selected for each country are the following:

Table 1.3.2 RWPPs identified by countries

Country	Original Party Name	Abbrev.	English party name
Germany	Alternative für Deutschland	AfD	Alternative for Germany
Denmark	Dansk Folkeparti	DF	Danish People's Party
	Nye Borgerlige	NB	The New Right
	Danmarksdemokraterne	DD	Danmark Democrats
Spain	Vox	Vox	Vox
	Aliança catalana	AC	Catalan Alliance
Hungary	FIDESZ – KDNP (Fidesz Magyar Polgári Párt, Kereszténydemokrata Néppárt)	FIDESZ–KDNP	Fidesz – Hungarian Civic Alliance
	Mi Hazánk (Mi Hazánk Mozgalom)	Mi Hazánk	Our Homeland Movement
UK	Brexit Party/Reform UK	BRX/Reform	Brexit Party/Reform UK
	United Kingdom Independence Party	UKIP	United Kingdom Independence Party
Switzerland	Schweizerische Volkspartei - German	SVP	Swiss People's Party
	Union Démocratique du Centre (UDC) - French	UDC	
	Unione Democratica di Centro - Italian	UDC	
	Eidgenössisch-Demokratische Union (EDU) - German	EDU	Federal Democratic Union
	Union Démocratique Fédérale (UDF) - French	UDF	
	Unione Democratica Federale (UDF) - Italian	UDF	
	Lega - German	Lega	Ticino League
Lega dei Ticinesi (Lega) - French/Italian	Lega		
Mouvement Citoyens Romand - German/French/Italian	MCR	Romandy Citizens' Movement	

Source: own elaboration based on official parliamentary and party websites.

Once the main field was completed, we proceeded to analyze the number of responses obtained from women and men in the case of the United Kingdom, who had question Q5- *Propensity to vote*. At the end of December, a complementary (boost) sample was added in order to obtain a specific sample of RWPP voters. This boost sample was transferred to a non- probability panel platform, which allowed for additional interviews in each country of the study. This strategy was key to ensure an adequate representation of this segment within the total sample.

1.4 Stages and implementation dates

All in all, the survey fieldwork was conducted in three distinct phases (Pilot, Main Field and Boost) in the six countries almost simultaneously. This situation required exhaustive coordination among all the countries in the study, together with the VERIAN, which centralized the programming and collection of information. DEUSTO played the role of central coordination and management unit that facilitated interaction between the different parts of the project, ensuring efficiency and information between participating countries. In addition, communication channels with VERIAN were established to resolve any incidents in an agile manner, thus ensuring compliance with the deadlines established for each phase. This collaborative approach allowed for smooth and effective data collection.

The main stages of data collection and their execution dates are detailed below:

Table 1.4.1 Start and closure of the pilot, main and boost fieldwork

Country	Date of departure Pilot fieldwork	Pilot fieldwork end date
United Kingdom	26/07/2024	03/08/2024
Germany	13/08/2024	19/08/2024
Denmark	06/08/2024	13/08/2024
Switzerland	16/08/2024	08/09/2024
Hungary	30/07/2024	19/08/2024
Spain	26/07/2024	11/09/2024
Country	Date of departure Main fieldwork	Main fieldwork end date
United Kingdom	23/10/2024	25/11/2024
Germany	25/10/2024	07/12/2024
Denmark	28/10/2024	09/01/2025
Switzerland	28/10/2024	01/12/2024
Hungary	30/10/2024	28/11/2024
Spain	29/10/2024	06/12/2024
Country	Release date Boost	End date Boost
United Kingdom	06/12/2024	17/12/2024
Germany	11/12/2024	17/12/2024

Denmark	24/12/2024	09/01/2025
Switzerland	11/12/2024	17/12/2024
Hungary	11/12/2024	17/12/2024
Spain	11/12/2024	17/12/2024

Source: Own elaboration based on Verian Fieldwork Report.

1.4.1 The collection

Specifically, the pilot took place from July 26 to September 11, 2024, the general data collection took place between October 23, 2024 and January 9, 2025, and finally, the Boost took place between December 6, 2024 and January 9, 2025.

These dates have already been noted earlier in the report, and it is important to emphasize that they were carefully established to ensure the smooth flow of the different phases of the study and the correct transition between them. The timing of the dates allowed not only for proper planning, but also for continuous monitoring of the progress of the work in each participating country. The closing of the field on January 9, 2025 marked the end of a key stage of the project, but also the beginning of the final analysis of the data collected.

1.4.2 Set Up

The set-up work began on April 18 and was completed on July 26, 2024, when the pilot study data collection work began. This set work was initially scheduled to be completed within two weeks, but due to the large volume of changes and correction of scheduling issues, the fieldwork had to be delayed beyond what was indicated in the initial protocol.

The programming issues were related to the questionnaire, which, although consolidated in the 6 countries, required modifications after its initial programming. This included adjustments to the texts and the consolidation of response options that had not been contemplated until that time.

1.4.3 Completion of Pilot - Start of Main Field

Once the pilot study fieldwork was completed, a series of changes were applied to the questionnaire. These changes ranged from typographical and spelling corrections to the elimination of questions and the modification of the questionnaire boarding. This task proved to be arduous and complex, since, due to the characteristics of the study, which is based on a questionnaire with multiple filters, generating multiple internal versions of the questionnaire that affected all the programmed countries.

The work in the main field was carried out without major incidents. The sampling objectives were met in all countries, except in the case of Denmark, where it was necessary to conduct ad hoc interviews in a non-probabilistic panel to cover the sample segment of the population aged 18 to 24 years.

1.4.4 Post Field- Quality:

A first delivery of the results obtained during the pilot study was made in order to examine the data collection and to carry out the different actions necessary for the modification of the questionnaire. It also served to test the functioning of the different probabilistic panels and to adjust the sample design. This delivery phase was crucial to make adjustments before proceeding with the main field, allowing us to identify any issues in time. Once the main field was completed, VERIAN applied rigorous controls to ensure the validity of the results:

-Removal of surveys: For quality reasons, all surveys with a duration of less than 5 minutes were automatically removed. It is considered that such a low duration is not admissible for the study, so these questionnaires were excluded in both the main study and the Boost.

-Response filters: Questionnaires whose content included "Don't know, No answer" or "Other" responses of more than 50% were also eliminated. This type of response could indicate a lack of understanding or active participation in the questionnaire.

-Verification with external sources: As part of the quality system, variables such as age, gender, education level, voting tendency, among others, were monitored during fieldwork. These variables were compared with statistical data from international studies, such as the ESS (European Social Survey) and data from the last elections in each country, to confirm that the survey results were aligned with official data trends and were representative of the target population.

The number of questionnaires deleted by country as a result of these quality controls were as follows:

Table 1.4.4.1 Number of questionnaires removed by country

Country	Main fieldwork	Boost
United Kingdom	53	37
Germany	14	10
Denmark	12	33

Switzerland	13	18
Hungary	71	15
Spain	16	24

Source: Own elaboration based on Verian Fieldwork Report.

After the removal of interviews, the main field or Boost phases were reactivated, as necessary, in those countries where gaps in the sample were detected. This step was crucial to ensure that the number of completed interviews met the established objectives and that the data obtained were representative. During this reactivation, the process was carefully monitored to ensure that the additional interviews maintained the same level of quality as the previous ones, thus allowing the final results to accurately reflect the characteristics of the target population.

1.4.5 Collection results:

Table 1.4.5.1 shows the final number of valid questionnaires collected in each phase of the survey. This table reflects in detail the results obtained in the different stages, including both the previous pilot, the main field and boost phases.

Table 1.4.5.1 Number of valid questionnaires collected in each phase by country

	Total	Interviews Field Boost +	Pilot Interviews	Interviews Main Field	Boost Interviews
United Kingdom	2.159	2.059	100	1.756	303
Germany	2.064	1.952	112	1.769	183
Denmark	1.317	1.211	106	1.005	206
Switzerland	1.327	1.212	115	1.009	203
Hungary	1.401	1.297	104	1.112	185
Spain	2.088	1.967	121	1.768	199
Total	10.356	9.698	658	8.419	1.279

Source: Own elaboration based on Verian Fieldwork Report

At the end of the collection, a total of 10,356 interviews had been obtained, of which 658 corresponded to the pilot study, 8,419 to the main field and 1,279 to the work related to the Boost. This means that a total of 9,698 valid interviews were obtained (excluding

those from the pilot study), which are considered representative of the population of each of the countries participating in the study.

1.5 Questionnaire

The study was conducted using as model the master UK questionnaire designed and translated into the official languages by the partners in WP6. This questionnaire consisted of 60 closed questions, with 110 response categories. It was design to capture detailed information on attitudes, opinions and behaviors related to the UNTWIST main hypothesis operationalization. In addition, socio-demographic questions were included to ensure a complete and segmented analysis of the data. The translation and adaptation of the questionnaire was carefully done to respect the cultural and linguistic particularities of each country.

The real average duration of the questionnaire in its practical CAWI application varied by country, as follows:

Table 1.5.1 Average time of questionnaire filling by country

Country	Minutes		
	Average time Pilot	Average Time Main Field	Average Boost time
United Kingdom	22,0	23,1	13,2
Germany	24,0	24,2	13,8
Denmark	27,4	23,8	16,3
Switzerland	24,8	23,7	15,7
Hungary	17,0	20,3	15,8
Spain	27,0	22,6	14,1

Source: Own elaboration based on Verian Fieldwork Report

Table 1.5.1 shows that in the Boost stage, the average response time is shorter compared to the main field. This is due to the type of panel used for each stage. As previously explained, a probabilistic panel was used for the main field, while a non-probabilistic panel was used for the Boost in all countries. In the latter, panelists are used to frequently responding to questionnaires and tend to do so more quickly than in a probabilistic panel, where participants are less experienced in this practice and therefore respond at a slower pace.

2. HARMONIZATION STRATEGY ON EDUCATION AND RELIGIOUS BELONGING

Data harmonization efforts were conducted in this process to provide comparability of datasets from mixed sources and allow for combining, pooling, or integrating them in a coherent way. Indeed, data pooling from multiple studies or countries into a single dataset provides opportunities to increase the statistical power of a study and to answer novel research questions that could not be addressed using data from a single study (Adhikari et al., 2021). To do this, we relied on the Integrated data from the European Social Survey (ESS) as our harmonization reference.

On the one hand, the education level variable particularly entailed one of the main challenges for the UNTWIST survey regarding comparability, given the high level of heterogeneity of educational categories in each country. To achieve this, we followed the harmonised ESS education variable, **EDULVLB**, a more detailed ISCED variable with 26 codes from round 5, which replaces the 7-category variable (EDULVL) that has been used in previous ESS rounds. Although not all the 26 codes apply in all countries. The EDULVLB variable contains a 3-digit hierarchical coding framework, which allows for the derivation of purpose-built educational measures/variables (See Appendix Education ESS11-2023).

Table 2.1 Highest level of education, EDULVLB

Code	Label
0	Not completed ISCED level 1
113	ISCED 1, completed primary education
129	Vocational ISCED 2C < 2 years, no access ISCED 3
212	General/pre-vocational ISCED 2A/2B, access ISCED 3 vocational
213	General ISCED 2A, access ISCED 3A general/all 3
221	Vocational ISCED 2C >= 2 years, no access ISCED 3
222	Vocational ISCED 2A/2B, access ISCED 3 vocational
223	Vocational ISCED 2, access ISCED 3 general/all
229	Vocational ISCED 3C < 2 years, no access ISCED 5
311	General ISCED 3 >=2 years, no access ISCED 5 *
312	General ISCED 3A/3B, access ISCED 5B/lower tier 5A
313	General ISCED 3A, access upper tier ISCED 5A/all 5
321	Vocational ISCED 3C >= 2 years, no access ISCED 5
322	Vocational ISCED 3A/3B, access 5B/lower tier 5A
323	Vocational ISCED 3A, access upper tier ISCED 5A/all 5
412	General ISCED 4A/4B, access ISCED 5B/lower tier 5A
413	General ISCED 4A, access upper tier ISCED 5A/all 5
421	ISCED 4 programmes without access ISCED 5
422	Vocational ISCED 4A/4B, access ISCED 5B/lower tier 5A

423	Vocational ISCED 4A, access upper tier ISCED 5A/all 5
510	ISCED 5A short, intermediate/academic/general tertiary below
520	ISCED 5B short, advanced vocational qualifications
610	ISCED 5A medium, bachelor/equivalent from lower tier tertiary
620	ISCED 5A medium, bachelor/equivalent from upper/single tier
710	ISCED 5A long, master/equivalent from lower tier tertiary
720	ISCED 5A long, master/equivalent from upper/single tier tertiary
800	ISCED 6, doctoral degree
5555	Other

* This code does not exist in ISCED.

Source: Appendix Education ESS11-2023

The UNTWIST harmonized education variable was generated from country specific variables, also retrieved from ESS-10/11 country questionnaires. These country specific measures have consequently changed to meet the more detailed requirements of the new harmonised target variable EDULVLB. As a result of the new approach, bridging specifications have been produced for all participating countries.

On the other hand, for the religious belonging variable, we followed the harmonised ESS10 “Religion or denomination to at present” variable, **rlgdnm**, with eight codes:

Table 2.2 Which religion do you belong to?

Code	Label
1	Roman Catholic
2	Protestant
3	Eastern Orthodox
4	Other Christian denomination
5	Jewish
6	Islam
7	Eastern religions
8	Other non-Christian religions

Source: ESS10 Self-completion – integrated file, edition 3.1

The tables below show the harmonization of the UNTWIST education variable based on the rules for construction of the variable EDULVL(B) from the country specific variables (Tables 2.3 - 2.10). Table 2.11 show the harmonization of the UNTWIST religion belonging variable based on the county specific variables retrieved from ESS10 countries questionnaires as well.

Table 2.3 Harmonization of education - United Kingdom

UNTWIST		ESS - EDULVL(B)	
Category	Code	Category	Code
Ph.D, D.Phil or equivalent 1	1	ISCED 6, doctoral degree	800
Masters Degree, M.Phil, Post-Graduate Diplomas and Certificates	2	ISCED 5A long, master/equivalent from upper/single tier tertiary	720
5 year University/CNAA first Degree (MB, BDS, BV etc)	3		
3-4 year University/CNAA first Degree (BA, BSc, BEd, BEng, etc)	4	ISCED 5A medium, bachelor/equivalent from upper/single tier	620
Nursing certificate, Teacher training HE Diploma Edexcel/BTEC/BEC/TEC - Higher National Diploma (HND) OCR/RSA - Higher Diploma City and Guilds - Level 4/Full Technological/Part IV NVQ/SVQ Level 4 or 5 or equivalent	5	ISCED 5B short, advanced vocational qualifications	520
Foundation Degree (FdA, FdSc etc) 6	6	ISCED 5A short, intermediate/academic/general tertiary below	510
Edexcel/BTEC/BEC/TEC - Higher National Certificate (HNC) or equivalent Certificate of Higher Education	7	Vocational ISCED 4A, access upper tier ISCED 5A /all 5	423
HE Access	8	General ISCED 4A, access upper tier ISCED 5A/all 5	413
Vocational A-level (AVCE), GCE Applied A-level NVQ/SVQ Level 3 GNVQ/GSVQ Advanced Edexcel/BTEC/BEC/TEC (General/Ordinary) National Certificate or Diploma (ONC/OND) City and Guilds Advanced (Level 3/Part III), Tech level	9	Vocational ISCED 3A, access upper tier ISCED 5A/all 5	323
(Modern) Apprenticeship, Advanced (Modern) Apprenticeship SVQ/NVQ/Key Skills Level 1 and 2 City and Guilds Craft/Intermediate (Levels 1 to 2/Parts I - II) RSA/OCR Vocational or First Certificate/Diploma, Advanced Diploma Edexcel/BTEC First/General Diploma, Technical Certificate, SCOTVEC/SQA National certificate modules	10	Vocational ISCED 3C >= 2 years, no access ISCED 5	321

2 or more A-levels or equivalent: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 or more A-levels, S-levels, A2-level • Scottish Highers, Scottish SCE/SLC/SUPE at Higher Grade, Scottish Higher School Certificate, Certificate of Sixth Year Studies/Advanced Higher Grade, Scottish Baccalaureate. • Welsh Advanced Baccalaureate • Irish Leaving Certificate • International Baccalaureate 	11	General ISCED 3A, access upper tier ISCED 5A/all 5	313
GNVQ or GSVQ Intermediate 2	12	Vocational ISCED 3C < 2 years, no access ISCED 5	229
Vocational GCSE or equivalent: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vocational GCSE • SCOTVEC/SQA National Courses • BTEC First/General Certificate • Technical Award 	13	Vocational ISCED 2A/2B, access ISCED 3 vocational	222
5 or more GCSEs A*-C or 4-9 or equivalent: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5 or more GCSEs A*-C or 4-9, CSE Grade 1, GCE O-level Grades A-C or 1-6 • Scottish SCE Ordinary Bands A-C or Pass, Scottish Standard Grades 1-3 or Pass • School Certificate or Matriculation • Scottish School Leaving Certificate Lower Grade, SUPE Ordinary, Scottish Intermediate 1 (A grade), Scottish Intermediate 2 • Intermediate/National Welsh Baccalaureate • Irish Junior Certificate • 1 A-level or equivalent 	14	General ISCED 2A, access ISCED 3A general/all 3	213
1-4 GCSEs A*-C or 4-9 or equivalent: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1-4 GCSEs A*-C or 4-9, GCSE Grades D-G or 1-3, Short course GCSE, CSE Grades 2-5, GCE O-level Grades D-E or 7-9 • Scottish (SCE) Ordinary Bands D-E, Scottish Standard Grades 4-7, Scottish School Leaving Certificate - no grade, Scottish Access 1-3, Scottish Intermediate 1 (below A grade) • GNVQ or GSVQ Foundation level • Foundation Welsh Baccalaureate 	15	General/pre-vocational ISCED 2A/2B, access ISCED3 vocational	212
Skills for Life (including Basic Skills, Key Skills, Entry Level Certificates).	16	ISCED 1, completed primary education	113
None of these	17	Not completed ISCED level 1	0

Source: own elaboration based on Appendix Education ESS11-2023 and ESS-10/11 country questionnaires.

Table 2.4 Harmonization of education - Denmark

UNTWIST		ESS - EDULVL(B)	
Category	Code	Category	Code
Ingen skolegang, Børnehaveklasse. 1.-5. klasse	1	Not completed ISCED level 1	0
Folkeskole 6.-8. klasse	2	ISCED 1, completed primary education	113
9. - 10. klasse	3	General ISCED 2A, access ISCED 3A general/all 3	213
Gymnasielle uddannelser, studentereksamen, HF, HHX, HTX	4	General ISCED 3A, access upper tier ISCED 5A/all 5	313
Kort erhvervsuddannelse under 1-2 års varighed, F.eks. AMU Arbejdsmarkedsuddannelser, Basisår på Erhvervsfaglige uddannelser	5	Vocational ISCED 3C < 2 years, no access ISCED 5	229
Faglig uddannelse (håndværk, handel, landbrug mv.), F.eks. Faglærte, Social- og sundhedsassistent-uddannelsen og tilsvarende	6	Vocational ISCED 3A/3B, access 5B/lower tier 5A	322
Kort videregående uddannelse af op til 2-3 års varighed, F.eks. Erhvervsakademiuddannelser f.eks. datamatiker, tandplejer, byggetekniker, installatør, HD	7	ISCED 5B short, advanced vocational qualifications	520
Mellemlang videregående uddannelse af 3-4 års varighed. professionsbachelor, F.eks. Diplomingeniør, sygeplejerske, skolelærer, pædagog, journalist, HA	8	ISCED 5A medium, bachelor/equivalent from lower tier tertiary	610
Universitetsbachelor. 1. del af kandidatuddannelsen	9	ISCED 5A medium, bachelor/equivalent from upper/single tier	620
Lang videregående uddannelse. Kandidatuddannelser af 5.-6. års varighed, F.eks. cand.mag., cand.jur., cand.polyt. etc.	10	ISCED 5A long, master/equivalent from upper/single tier tertiary	720
Licentiat	11		
Forskeruddannelse. Ph.d., doktor	12	ISCED 6, doctoral degree	800

Source: own elaboration based on Appendix Education ESS11-2023 and ESS-10/11 country questionnaires.

Table 2.5 Harmonization of education - Hungary

UNTWIST		ESS - EDULVL(B)	
Category	Code	Category	Code
Nem járt iskolába; 1–3 osztály általános vagy azzal egyenértékű	1	Not completed ISCED level 1	0
4–7 osztály általános vagy azzal egyenértékű	2	ISCED 1, completed primary education	113
Befejezett általános iskola vagy azzal egyenértékű	3	General ISCED 2A, access ISCED 3A general/all 3	213
Szaktanácsképző, szakiskola	4	Vocational ISCED 3C >= 2 years, no access ISCED 5	321
10. évfolyamra épülő szakképzés	5		
Érettségi, befejezett szakközépiskola	6	Vocational ISCED 3A, access upper tier ISCED 5A/all 5	323
Érettségi, befejezett gimnázium	7	General ISCED 3A, access upper tier ISCED 5A/all 5	313
Érettségire épülő, felsőfokra nem akkreditált szakképzés, középfokú technikum	8	Vocational ISCED 4A, access upper tier ISCED 5A /all 5	423
Felsőfokú akkreditált szakképzés, felsőfokú technikum	9	ISCED 5B short, advanced vocational qualifications	520
Főiskolai diploma vagy főiskolai alapképzési szak – BA/BSC	10	ISCED 5A medium, bachelor/equivalent from lower tier tertiary	610
Egyetemi alapképzési szak – BA /BSC	11	ISCED 5A medium, bachelor/equivalent from upper/single tier	620
Főiskolai mesterképzési szak – MA/MSC	12	ISCED 5A long, master/equivalent from lower tier tertiary	710
Egyetemi diploma vagy egyetemi mesterképzési szak – MA/MSC	13	ISCED 5A long, master/equivalent from upper/single tier tertiary	720
Felsőfokú végzettség tudományos fokozattal	14	ISCED 6, doctoral degree	800

Source: own elaboration based on Appendix Education ESS11-2023 and ESS-10/11 country questionnaires.

Table 2.6 Harmonization of education - Spain

UNTWIST		ESS - EDULVL(B)	
Category	Code	Category	Code
Doctorado	1	ISCED 6, doctoral degree	800
Licenciatura, Máster oficial, Ingeniería Superior, Arquitectura, Título Superior en Música, Danza o Arte Dramático	2	ISCED 5A long, master/equivalent from upper/single tier tertiary	720
Diplomatura, Grado, Ingeniería Técnica, Arquitectura Técnica, 3 años de licenciatura, Título Superior en Diseño	3	ISCED 5A medium, bachelor/equivalent from upper/single tier	620
Peritaje, Antiguas Escuelas de Enfermería, de Magisterio o de Asistencia Social	4		
Bachillerato (LOGSE)	5	General ISCED 3A, access upper tier ISCED 5A/all 5	313
PREU, COU	6		
Bachillerato Superior, BUP	7	Vocational ISCED 3C < 2 years, no access ISCED 5	229
ESO (Completa)	8	General ISCED 2A, access ISCED 3A general/all 3	213
EGB (completa)	9		
Bachillerato Elemental	10		
Educación primaria (Certificado de Estudios primarios, hasta 5º de EGB incluido Primaria LOGSE)	11	ISCED 1, completed primary education	113
Menos de 5 años de escuela (estudios primarios sin completar)	12	Not completed ISCED level 1	0
No ha ido nunca a la escuela (sin estudios)	13		

Source: own elaboration based on Appendix Education ESS11-2023 and ESS-10/11 country questionnaires.

Table 2.7 Harmonization of education - Germany

UNTWIST		ESS - EDULVL(B)	
Category	Code	Category	Code
Promotion oder Habilitation	1	ISCED 6, doctoral degree	800
Diplom, Master, Magister oder Staatsexamen einer Universität (auch Kunst-, Musik-, technische, theologische oder pädagogische Hochschule)	2	ISCED 5A long, master/equivalent from upper/single tier tertiary	720
Master einer Fachhochschule (FH) (auch duale Hochschule)	3	ISCED 5A long, master/equivalent from lower tier tertiary	710
Bachelor einer Universität (auch Kunst-, Musik-, technische, theologische oder pädagogische Hochschule)	4	ISCED 5A medium, bachelor/equivalent from upper/single tier	620
Bachelor einer Fachhochschule (FH), Berufsakademie (auch duale Hochschule); Diplom (FH)	5	ISCED 5A medium, bachelor/equivalent from lower tier tertiary	610
Diplom einer Berufsakademie (BA)	6	ISCED 5B short, advanced vocational qualifications	520
Techniker- oder gleichwertiger Fachschulabschluss (inkl. Fachschule der ehemaligen DDR); Abschluss einer Fachakademie (Bayern)	7		
Meister	8		
Abschluss einer Lehre (Facharbeiter-, Gesellen- oder Kaufmannsgehilfenbrief, IHK-Prüfungszeugnis)	9	Vocational ISCED 3A/3B, access 5B/lower tier 5A	322
Abschluss einer Ausbildung zum Erzieher/zur Erzieherin	10	ISCED 5B short, advanced vocational qualifications	520
Berufsqualifizierender Abschluss einer Berufsfachschule/eines Kollegs (schulische Berufsausbildung)	11	Vocational ISCED 3A/3B, access 5B/lower tier 5A	322
Abschluss einer 2- bis 3-jährigen Ausbildung an einer Schule des Gesundheitswesens (medizinische Assistenten, Gesundheits- und Krankenpfleger/-pflegerin)	12	Vocational ISCED 3C >= 2 years, no access ISCED 5	321
Abschluss einer 1-jährigen Ausbildung an einer Schule des Gesundheitswesens (medizinische Hilfsberufe)	13	Vocational ISCED 3A/3B, access 5B/lower tier 5A	322
Betriebliche Anlernzeit mit Abschlusszeugnis, aber keine Lehre	14	Vocational ISCED 3C < 2 years, no access ISCED 5	229

Abitur, allgemeine oder fachgebundene Hochschulreife	15	Vocational ISCED 3A/3B, access 5B/lower tier 5A	322
Fachhochschulreife	16	General ISCED 3A, access upper tier ISCED 5A/all 5	313
Realschulabschluss, Mittlere Reife oder gleichwertiger Abschluss bzw. Polytechnische Oberschule der ehem. DDR mit Abschluss der 10. Klasse	17	General ISCED 3A/3B, access ISCED 5B/lower tier 5A	312
Volks- oder Hauptschulabschluss oder gleichwertiger Abschluss bzw. Polytechnische Oberschule der ehem. DDR mit Abschluss der 8. oder 9. Klasse	18	General ISCED 2A, access ISCED 3A general/all 3	213
(Noch) kein Schulabschluss, aber Grundschule (4. Klasse) beendet oder Abschluss einer Förderschule/Sonderschule	19	General/pre-vocational ISCED 2A/2B, access ISCED3 vocational	212
Grundschule (4. Klasse) nicht beendet	20	ISCED 1, completed primary education	113
Keinen der aufgelisteten Abschlüsse	21	Not completed ISCED level 1	0

Source: own elaboration based on Appendix Education ESS11-2023 and ESS-10/11 country questionnaires.

Table 2.8 Harmonization of education - Switzerland – German language

UNTWIST		ESS - EDULVL(B)	
Category	Code	Category	Code
Nicht abgeschlossene Primarschule	1	Not completed ISCED level 1	0
Primarschule (4 bis 6 Jahre Schule)	2	ISCED 1, completed primary education	113
Sekundar-, Real- und Oberschule (auch Primarschule von 8-9 Schuljahren)	3	General ISCED 2A, access ISCED 3A general/all 3	213
10. Schuljahr, Vorlehre, Haushaltsjahr, Berufsvorbereitungsklasse, Brückenangebote	4	General/pre-vocational ISCED 2A/2B, access ISCED3 vocational	212
Fachmittelschulen (3 Jahre, FMS-Ausweis, Fachmaturität), Diplommittelschulen (DMS), Handelsschule	5	General ISCED 3A/3B, access ISCED 5B/lower tier 5A	312
Gymnasiale Maturität, Gymnasium	6	General ISCED 3A, access upper tier ISCED 5A/all 5	313
Gymnasiale Maturität für Erwachsene oder Berufslehre nach gymnasialer Maturität	7	Vocational ISCED 4A, access upper tier ISCED 5A /all 5	423
Lehrerseminar, Schule für Unterrichtsberufe (für Vor- und Primarschule)	8	Vocational ISCED 3A, access upper tier ISCED 5A/all 5	323
Berufsmaturität	9	Vocational ISCED 3A/3B, access 5B/lower tier 5A	322
Berufsmaturität für Erwachsene	10	Vocational ISCED 4A/4B, access ISCED 5B/lower tier 5A	422
Berufliche Grundbildung (Eidg. Berufsattest) Anlehre in Betrieb und Schule, Kurzlehre (2 Jahre), Handelsschule (1 Jahr), Allgemeinbildende Schule (1-2 Jahre)	11	Vocational ISCED 3C < 2 years, no access ISCED 5	229
Berufslehre 3-4 Jahre (Eidg. Fähigkeitszeugnis) in Lehrbetrieb oder in Berufsfachschule	12		
Zweite Berufslehre oder Berufslehre als Zweitausbildung	13	Vocational ISCED 3A/3B, access 5B/lower tier 5A	322
Meisterdiplom, Eidg. Fachausweis und weitere Fachprüfungen	14	ISCED 4 programmes without access ISCED 5	421

Diplom oder Nachdiplom einer höheren Fachschule, z.B. in den Bereichen Technik, Verwaltung, Gesundheit, Sozialarbeit, Kunst und Gestaltung	15	ISCED 5B short, advanced vocational qualifications	520
Diplom oder Nachdiplom einer der folgenden höheren Fachschulen: Ingenieurschule (HTL); Höhere Wirtschafts- und Verwaltungsschule (HWV); Höhere Fachschule für Gestaltung (HFG); Höhere Hauswirtschaftliche Fachschule (HHF); Hotelfachschule Lausanne (Abschlüsse der Jahre 1998, 1999 und 2000)	16		
Bachelor einer Fachhochschule (FH), Pädagogische Hochschule (PH)	17	ISCED 5A medium, bachelor/equivalent from lower tier tertiary	610
Master, Diplom oder Nachdiplom einer Fachhochschule (FH), Pädagogischen Hochschule	18	ISCED 5A long, master/equivalent from lower tier tertiary	710
Abgeschlossenes Grundstudium oder Halblizenziat einer universitären Hochschule	19	ISCED 5A short, intermediate/academic/general tertiary below	510
Bachelor oder Lizenziat (3-4 Jahre) einer universitären Hochschule oder Eidgenössischen Technischen Hochschule (ETH)	20	ISCED 5A medium, bachelor/equivalent from upper/single tier	620
Lizenziat (mehr als 4 Jahre) einer universitären Hochschule oder Eidgenössischen Technischen Hochschule (ETH)	21	ISCED 5A long, master/equivalent from upper/single tier tertiary	720
Master, Diplom oder Nachdiplom einer universitären Hochschule oder Eidgenössischen Technischen Hochschule (ETH)	22		
Doktorat, PhD	23	ISCED 6, doctoral degree	800

Source: own elaboration based on Appendix Education ESS11-2023 and ESS-10/11 country questionnaires.

Table 2.9 Harmonization of education - Switzerland – French language

UNTWIST		ESS - EDULVL(B)	
Category	Code	Category	Code
Ecole primaire inachevée	1	Not completed ISCED level 1	0
Ecole primaire (4 à 6 ans de scolarité)	2	ISCED 1, completed primary education	113
Cycle d'orientation, école secondaire	3	General ISCED 2A, access ISCED 3A general/all 3	213
10. année, préapprentissage, cours préparatoire, école préprofessionnelle	4	General/pre-vocational ISCED 2A/2B, access ISCED3 vocational	212
Ecoles de culture générale (3 ans, certificat d'ECG, maturité spécialisée), Ecoles de degré diplôme (EDD), Haute Ecole de commerce (HEC)	5	General ISCED 3A/3B, access ISCED 5B/lower tier 5A	312
Maturité gymnasiale, Gymnase, Collège	6	General ISCED 3A, access upper tier ISCED 5A/all 5	313
Maturité gymnasiale pour adultes ou apprentissage après maturité gymnasiale	7	Vocational ISCED 4A, access upper tier ISCED 5A /all 5	423
Ecole normale, Etudes pédagogiques (niveau préscolaire et primaire)	8	Vocational ISCED 3A, access upper tier ISCED 5A/all 5	323
Maturité professionnelle	9	Vocational ISCED 3A/3B, access 5B/lower tier 5A	322
Maturité professionnelle pour adultes	10	Vocational ISCED 4A/4B, access ISCED 5B/lower tier 5A	422
Formation professionnelle initiale (Attestation fédérale de formation professionnelle, Apprentissage court (2 ans), Ecole commerciale (1 an), Ecole de formation générale (1-2 ans)	11	Vocational ISCED 3C < 2 years, no access ISCED 5	229
Apprentissage 3-4 ans (CFC) en entreprise formatrice ou en école professionnelle	12	Vocational ISCED 3A/3B, access 5B/lower tier 5A	322
Deuxième apprentissage ou apprentissage en tant que deuxième formation	13	ISCED 4 programmes without access ISCED 5	421
Maîtrise professionnelle, brevet fédéral et autres examens professionnels supérieurs	14	ISCED 5B short, advanced vocational qualifications	520

Diplôme ou postgrade d'une école professionnelle supérieure, p.ex. dans les domaines techniques, administration, santé, travail social, arts appliqués	15		
Diplôme ou postgrade d'une des écoles supérieures suivantes: écoles d'ingénieurs ETS écoles supérieures de cadres pour l'économie et l'administration (ESCEA) écoles supérieures d'arts appliqués (ESAA) écoles supérieures d'économie familiale (ESEF) école hôtelière de Lausanne (EHL, diplômes décernés en 1998, 1999 et 2000)	16		
Hautes écoles spécialisées (HES), Hautes écoles pédagogiques (HEP): Bachelor	17	ISCED 5A medium, bachelor/equivalent from lower tier tertiary	610
Hautes écoles spécialisées (HES), Hautes écoles pédagogiques (HEP): Master, diplôme, postgrade	18	ISCED 5A long, master/equivalent from lower tier tertiary	710
Hautes écoles universitaires, écoles polytechniques fédérale (EPF): Demi-licence, certificat propédeutique*	19	ISCED 5A short, intermediate/academic/general tertiary below	510
Hautes écoles universitaires, écoles polytechniques fédérale (EPF): Bachelor, licence en 3-4 ans	20	ISCED 5A medium, bachelor/equivalent from upper/single tier	620
Hautes écoles universitaires, écoles polytechniques fédérale (EPF): Licence exigeant plus que 4 ans	21	ISCED 5A long, master/equivalent from upper/single tier tertiary	720
Hautes écoles universitaires, écoles polytechniques fédérale (EPF): Master, diplôme, postgrade	22		
Hautes écoles universitaires, écoles polytechniques fédérale (EPF): Doctorat, PhD	23	ISCED 6, doctoral degree	800

*19 S. Hautes écoles universitaires, demi-licence, certificat propédeutique: Since the Bologna-reform (2005), this diploma is no longer attainable from Swiss Universities

Source: own elaboration based on Appendix Education ESS11-2023 and ESS-10/11 country questionnaires.

Table 2.10 Harmonization of education - Switzerland – Italian language

UNTWIST		ESS - EDULVL(B)	
Category	Code	Category	Code
Scuola elementare non terminata	1	Not completed ISCED level 1	0
Scuola elementare (scolarità di 4 a 6 anni)	2	ISCED 1, completed primary education	113
Scuola secondaria, scuola media (e scuola elementare di 8-9 anni)	3	General ISCED 2A, access ISCED 3A general/all 3	213
10. anno, pretirocinio, corso preprofessionale, offerte transitorie	4	General/pre-vocational ISCED 2A/2B, access ISCED3 vocational	212
Scuole specializzate (3 anni, certificato, maturità specializzata) scuola per professioni sanitarie/sociali (sspss), scuole di diploma (SDD), scuola commerciale	5	General ISCED 3A/3B, access ISCED 5B/lower tier 5A	312
Maturità ginnasiale, Liceo	6	General ISCED 3A, access upper tier ISCED 5A/all 5	313
Maturità ginnasiale per adulti o apprendistato dopo maturità ginnasiale	7	Vocational ISCED 4A, access upper tier ISCED 5A /all 5	423
Scuola magistrale, patente di maestro/a (per scuola dell'infanzia e scuola elementare)	8	Vocational ISCED 3A, access upper tier ISCED 5A/all 5	323
Maturità professionale	9	Vocational ISCED 3A/3B, access 5B/lower tier 5A	322
Maturità professionale per adulti	10	Vocational ISCED 4A/4B, access ISCED 5B/lower tier 5A	422
Formazione professionale di base (Certificato federale di formazione pratica), Apprendistato corto (2 anni), Scuole commerciali (1 anno), Scuole di formazione generale (1-2 anni)	11	Vocational ISCED 3C < 2 years, no access ISCED 5	229
Apprendistato 3-4 anni (AFC: attestato federale di capacità) tirocinio in azienda o in scuola professionale di base	12	Vocational ISCED 3A/3B, access 5B/lower tier 5A	322
Secondo apprendistato o apprendistato come seconda formazione	13	ISCED 4 programmes without access ISCED 5	421
Maestria, brevetto federale e altri esami professionali superiori	14	ISCED 5B short, advanced vocational qualifications	520

Diploma o postdiploma di una scuola professionale superiore, p.es. nel campo tecnico, amministrativo, salute, lavoro sociale, arte applicata	15		
Diploma o postdiploma di una delle seguenti scuole superiori: • scuola tecnica superiore (STS) • scuola superiore dei quadri per l'economia e l'amministrazione (SSQEA) • scuola superiore di arti applicate (SSAA) • scuola superiore di economia domestica (SSED) • scuola alberghiera di Losanna (titoli conseguiti negli anni 1998, 1999 e 2000)	16		
Scuole universitarie professionali (SUP), Alte scuole pedagogiche (ASP): Bachelor	17	ISCED 5A medium, bachelor/equivalent from lower tier tertiary	610
Scuole universitarie professionali (SUP), Alte scuole pedagogiche (ASP): Master, licenza, diploma, postdiploma	18	ISCED 5A long, master/equivalent from lower tier tertiary	710
Università, Politecnico Federale: Biennio propedeutico, primo ciclo con certificato	19	ISCED 5A short, intermediate/academic/general tertiary below	510
Università, Politecnico Federale: Bachelor, licenza in 3-4 anni	20	ISCED 5A medium, bachelor/equivalent from upper/single tier	620
Università, Politecnico Federale: Licenza che esige più di 4 anni di studio	21	ISCED 5A long, master/equivalent from upper/single tier tertiary	720
Università, Politecnico Federale: Master, licenza, diploma, postdiploma	22		
Università, Politecnico Federale: Dottorato, PhD	23	ISCED 6, doctoral degree	800

Source: own elaboration based on Appendix Education ESS11-2023 and ESS-10/11 country questionnaires.

Table 2.11 Harmonization of religious belonging

UNTWIST HARMONIZED CATEGORIES	UK	Denmark	Spain	Hungary	Germany	Switzerland
1 Roman Catholic	1 Roman Catholic	2 Romersk- katolsk	2 Católica	2 Római katolikus	1 Römisch-Katholische Kirche	1 Catholique
2 Protestant	2 Church of England / Anglican 3 Church of Ireland 4 Baptist 5 Methodist 6 Presbyterian / Church of Scotland 7 United Reformed Church / Congregational 8 Free Presbyterian 9 Brethren 10 Other Protestant	3 Protestantisk	3 Protestante	3 Református vagy evangélikus	2 Evangelisch/ Protestantisch Kirche (EKD, ohne Freikirche) 3 Evangelische Freikirche	2 Protestante
3 Eastern Orthodox	11 Greek or Russian Orthodox 12 Other Eastern Orthodox	4 Østlig ortodoks	4 Ortodoxa	4 Keleti ortodox	4 Östlich-Orthodoxe Glaubensgemeinschaft	3 Orthodoxe
4 Other Christian denomination	13 Other Christian	5 Andre kristne religioner	5 Otras confesiones cristianas	5 Egyéb keresztény felekezet	5 Andere christliche Konfession	4 Autre confession chrétienne
5 Jewish	18 Jewish	6 Jødisk	6 Judía	6 Zsidó	6 Judentum	5 Juive

6 Islam	19 Islam /Muslim	7 Islam	7 Musulmana	7 Iszlám	7 Muslimische Glaubensgemeinschaft/Islam	6 Islamique
7 Eastern religions	14 Hindu 15 Sikh 16 Buddhist 17 Other Eastern Religions	8 Østlige religioner	8 Religiones orientales (budista, hindú, sij, sintoísta, taoísta)	8 Keleti vallások	8 Östliche Religionsgemeinschaft (Buddhismus, Hinduismus, Sikh, Shinto, Tao etc.)	7 Religions orientales
8 Other non-Christian religions	20 Other non-Christian	9 Andre ikke kristne religioner	9 Otras religiones no cristianas	9 Egyéb nem keresztény vallás	9 Andere nicht-christliche Religionsgemeinschaft	8 Autres religions non chrétiennes
9 I do not consider myself to belong to any particular religion or denomination.		1 Jeg tilhører ikke en bestemt religion eller trosretning	1 No, no me considero perteneciente a ninguna religión o confesión en particular	1 Nem tartom magam egyetlen valláshoz vagy felekezethez sem tartozónak		9 Je ne me considère pas comme appartenant à une religion ou à une confession particulière
10 Other			10 Otra: por favor, anote cuál			

Source: own elaboration based on ESS10 integrated file and ESS-10/11 country questionnaires.

3. WEIGHTING

This section outlines the post-fieldwork weighting procedure applied in the survey to ensure that the sample accurately represents the target population within each country based on key demographic characteristics, taking into account the different sample designs across countries.

Once the fieldwork was completed and the quality work had been carried out, VERIAN run the corresponding weightings and adjusted the representativeness of the sample and consequently the responses obtained as much as possible. The description of the weighing procedure below is based on the weighting strategy report delivered by VERIAN a at the end of the fieldwork.

3.1 Importance and objectives of using weighted data

The willingness to participate in online surveys tend to differ across different demographic groups in the population and is reflected in different profiles of respondents vs non-respondents. In order to mitigate for non-response bias, it is important to apply calibration weights for key demographic characteristics. For this survey, the calibration weight considered gender, age, education, and region². Without weights, the estimates may be biased. This includes point estimates e.g. means and percentages, correlation coefficients, as well as measures of variance such as standard errors, confidence intervals and hypothesis tests. An illustrative example of the width of the confidence intervals using weighted and unweighted data is shown in section 3.7.

The weighting approach aims to achieve the following two objectives:

1. Ensure the main sample was representative of the target population within each country in relation to key demographic characteristics (gender, age, region, and educational attainment).
2. Ensure the full sample comprising both the main and boost sample within each country was representative of the target population in relation to the key demographic characteristics (as above) and the proportion of adults likely to vote for RWPPs (score 8-10 on the likelihood to vote question). As the proportion of adults likely to vote for RWPP is unknown, we used the demographically weighted data for the main sample to estimate this proportion when weighting the main+boost sample.

² In the case of Spain and Hungary, an additional weighting of region was applied, as the questionnaire question related to the region in these two countries requested information at a very low level. In contrast, the other countries had a higher level, making additional weighting unnecessary.

We describe the different steps involved in the weighting process in the sections further below.

3.2 Weighting factors in the dataset

The final weights included in the weighted dataset are labelled as follows:

- The variable **WgtMain** is the weight to use for the main sample. This is the final trimmed RIM weight, adjusting for gender, age, educational attainment, and region.
- The variable **WgtMainBoost** is the weight to use for the full sample. This is the final trimmed RIM weight, adjusting for gender, age, educational attainment, region and propensity to vote for RWPP (score 8-10) by gender.

3.3 Recommendations for using the datasets

As mentioned above, the dataset comprises a main sample and a boost sample. It is recommended that the main sample only is used for topline analysis that does not disaggregate the results by different sub-groups, for example the overall proportions of adults likely to vote for different political parties within each country. It is recommended using the main only dataset for such analysis, since fewer adjustments are made to ensure representativeness. Consequently, the weighting factors are generally smaller and the sample is statistically more efficient compared to the combined main + boost sample. There is also lower risk of potential bias due to different underlying characteristics between the main sample and the boost sample which are not captured by the variables used for weighting. For analysis using the main only dataset, the weighting factor WgtMain should be applied.

The boost sample was designed to collect responses from a sufficiently large sample of RWPP voters to allow for statistically robust and meaningful analysis. It is therefore recommended that the full sample (i.e. main + boost) is used for analysis involving sub-groups, such as comparing the demographic profile of adults likely to vote for RWPPs vs adults who are not likely to vote for RWPPs. For analysis using the full dataset, the weighting factor WgtMainBoost should be applied.

3.4 Weighting targets

Calibration weights were applied to ensure that the achieved samples matched the population profile for the 18+ population in each country on gender, age group, region, and educational attainment. The demographic targets are based on the latest population data on Eurostat. For all countries except the UK, the population parameters are from 2023. For the UK, they are from 2019. Data for the United Kingdom is not updated as frequently by Eurostat, and

educational attainment for 18+ and regional populations for 18+ were not readily available for more recent years. While population by gender and age was available for more recent periods, it is expected that the distribution by gender and age group will not noticeably have changed since 2019. It is therefore used 2019 data for all weighting targets for the UK.

The specific weighting targets were set using the following categories:

- Gender: Male/female
- Age group: 18-24, 25-39, 40-54, 55-65, and 65+
- Region: NUTS1 in DE, UK, and ES and NUTS 2 in DE, HU, CH
- Educational attainment: ISCED codes 0-2, 3-4 and 5+³

The population targets were adjusted based on the above categories to reflect the proportion of missing values in the achieved sample. This is because it is necessary to ensure respondents who did not supply information on one or more of the weighting variables were still kept in the sample. To do this the population data is re-allocated to reflect the proportion of missing values. For example, if the sample had 50% male, 49% females and 1% missing, then we would re-allocate the population data so that 1% was missing. Then the updated population figures are used as weighting targets. In the example above, if the population figures were 50%:50%, they would then become 49.5%: 49.5%:1%. The share of respondents who refused to state their gender, age, or educational attainment was minimal, however, ranging between 0% and 0.4% for the different variables across the six countries.

Additionally, for the main and boost sample combined, a weighting target for the proportion of RWPP voters is included (based on the share of this group in the main sample). The weighting targets for this variable were set using the following categories broken down by gender: Men unlikely to vote RWPP (score 0-7), Men likely to vote RWPP (score 8-10), Women unlikely to vote RWPP, Women likely to vote RWPP, Unknown gender unlikely to vote RWPP, Unknown gender likely to vote RWPP.

3.5 Weighting strategy

Two sets of calibration (RIM) weights are derived: One set of weights for the main sample only and one set of weights for the main and boost sample combined. For the main sample, a calibration weight is derived for gender, age, region, and educational attainment. Weights are

³ Educational attainment was only available for the 15+ population and by different broad age brackets within each ISCED category. In order to get educational attainment for the 18+ population, we therefore used figures for the 15-24 and 18-24 age brackets to adjust the 15+ population to reflect the 18+ population (we subtracted the 15-17 population from the 15+ population based on the difference between the 15-24 and 18-24 populations).

derived separately for each country, trimmed where necessary (see details below) and then combined the different weighted country datasets into a single file.

For the main and boost sample, a calibration weight is derived for gender, age, region, educational attainment, and the proportion of adults likely to vote for a RWPP. For the latter, the weighted estimate from the main sample is used and applied that as a weighting target for the combined sample. For example, if 10% of the main sample had women likely to vote for a RWPP, the combined main and boost sample was re-weighted to reflect this proportion by applying an additional rim of 10% of all women likely to vote for a RWPP. As for the main sample, the weights are derived separately for each country and then combined the country files into a single file.

Both sets of RIM weights are derived using the SPSS Rake command. Additionally, for the main samples for Germany and the UK, a design weight is first applied to reflect respondents' probability of selection from the probabilistic panel. These weights were already calculated and therefore simply applied to the dataset using a unique respondent ID for matching. The design weight was applied as a pre-weight before deriving the calibration weights.

For the other countries (DK, HU, ES, and CH), the panel partners do not collect the information required to derive design weights. It is therefore assumed that panellists had an equal probability of selection.

3.6 Trimming and weighting efficiency

Once the weights have been derived, outliers and cases with large weighting factors were controlled. If there were such cases, the weights were trimmed using percentile trimming. The weights were capped for each country separately. The specific thresholds used were based on the country distribution and presence of outliers. Table 3.6 below indicates the specific thresholds applied for each country (if any).

Weighting efficiency shows the amount of distortion needed to arrive at the weighted figures, in other words how much the data is manipulated by the weighting. It is shown as a percentage, with a higher percentage indicating more efficient weights. The weighting efficiency ranges between 68.4% (the UK) and 91.2% (Denmark) for the main sample only. The weighting efficiency is somewhat lower for the main and boost sample combined, as expected, since those weights include an additional rim to adjust for the boost sample. Note the weighting efficiency for the UK is a bit lower than the other countries, due to particular outliers which were removed in the trimming.

Table 3.6.1 Trimming thresholds and weighting efficiency

Country	Trimming threshold (lower/upper percentile)	Main sample	Country	Trimming threshold (lower/upper percentile)	Main sample + boost
Denmark	None	91.2%	Denmark	None	79.0%
Hungary	1/95	76.6%	Hungary	10/97	62.0%
Spain	None	73.2%	Spain	None	67.9%
Switzerland	1/98	70.9%	Switzerland	5/98	67.1%
Germany	3/97	74.5%	Germany	5/97	70.0%
UK	2/98	68.4%	UK	5/98	63.8%

Source: Own elaboration based on Verian Weighting Strategy Report.

3.7 Level of precision using weighted and unweighted data

The tables 3.7.1 and 3.7.2 show the unweighted and weighted point estimates of the proportion of adults likely to vote RWPP and associated 95% confidence intervals. The tables illustrate the importance of applying weights when carrying out analysis to ensure the results are unbiased.

Table 3.7.1 Percentage likely to vote RWPPs and 95% CI: Main sample only

Country	Unweighted			Weighted		
	Percentage	Lower 95%CI	Upper 95% CI	Percentage	Lower 95%CI	Upper 95% CI
UK	12.3%	10.8%	13.8%	13.3%	11.7%	14.9%
Denmark	16.1%	13.8%	18.4%	16.7%	14.4%	19.0%
Hungary	17.3%	15.0%	19.6%	17.5%	15.2%	19.9%
Spain	8.6%	7.3%	9.9%	8.6%	7.3%	10.0%
Germany	9.4%	8.0%	10.7%	10.9%	9.5%	12.4%
Switzerland	23.0%	20.4%	25.6%	23.4%	20.8%	26.0%

Source: Own elaboration based on Verian Weighting Strategy Report

Table 3.7.2 Percentage likely to vote RWPPs and 95% CI: Main + boost sample

Country	Unweighted			Weighted		
	Percentage	Lower 95%CI	Upper 95% CI	Percentage	Lower 95%CI	Upper 95% CI
UK	25.2%	23.3%	27.1%	13.9%	12.4%	15.4%
Denmark	30.4%	27.8%	33.0%	16.7%	14.6%	18.8%
Hungary	30.1%	27.5%	32.7%	18.4%	16.2%	20.6%
Spain	17.8%	16.2%	19.5%	8.6%	7.4%	9.8%
Germany	17.9%	16.2%	19.6%	11.4%	10.0%	12.8%
Switzerland	35.9%	33.2%	38.6%	24.3%	21.8%	26.7%

Source: Own elaboration based on Verian Weighting Strategy Report.

Appendix: Weighted and unweighted demographic profile

The tables below show the unweighted and weighted (WgtMain) distributions by gender, age group, and education.

Table 3.A.1 Unweighted and weighted distribution by Gender

	<i>Male %</i>		<i>Female %</i>		<i>Missing %</i>		<i>Total</i>	
	<i>Unweighted</i>	<i>WgtMain</i>	<i>Unweighted</i>	<i>WgtMain</i>	<i>Unweighted</i>	<i>WgtMain</i>	<i>Unw</i>	<i>Wgt</i>
<i>UK</i>	47.8	48.4	51.5	50.7	0.7	0.9	100	100
<i>DK</i>	42.5	49.0	56.9	50.3	0.6	0.7	100	100
<i>HU</i>	42.3	47.2	57.4	52.4	0.3	0.4	100	100
<i>ES</i>	44.3	48.5	55.6	51.4	0.1	0.1	100	100
<i>DE</i>	44.3	48.3	55.4	51.3	0.3	0.4	100	100
<i>CH</i>	38.2	48.7	61.6	51.1	0.2	0.2	100	100
<i>Base</i>	4203	4022	5359	4260	36	38	9598	8320

Source: Own elaboration based on Verian Weighting Strategy Report.

Table 3.A.2 Unweighted and weighted distribution by Age group

	<i>18-24 %</i>		<i>35-39 %</i>		<i>40-54 %</i>		<i>Total</i>	
	<i>Unweighted</i>	<i>WgtMain</i>	<i>Unweighted</i>	<i>WgtMain</i>	<i>Unweighted</i>	<i>WgtMain</i>		
<i>UK</i>	8.4	11	25.4	25.8	26.2	25.3		
<i>DK</i>	9.3	10.8	27.8	24.1	23.4	23.4		
<i>HU</i>	8.5	9.0	23.5	22.9	28.9	28.6		
<i>ES</i>	9.6	8.8	21.3	21.2	30.7	29.0		
<i>DE</i>	6.2	8.1	26.7	25.8	26.0	23.6		
<i>CH</i>	8.1	9.0	24.3	24.6	26.2	25.7		
<i>Base</i>	795	784	2377	2006	2597	2156		

	<i>55-64 %</i>		<i>65+ %</i>		<i>Missing %</i>		<i>Total</i>	
	<i>Unweighted</i>	<i>WgtMain</i>	<i>Unweighted</i>	<i>WgtMain</i>	<i>Unweighted</i>	<i>WgtMain</i>	<i>Unw</i>	<i>Wgt</i>
<i>UK</i>	17.1	15.5	22.8	22.4	0.0	0.1	100	100
<i>DK</i>	15.2	16.3	24.3	25.4	0.0	0.0	100	100
<i>HU</i>	15.8	14.6	23.3	24.9	0.0	0.0	100	100
<i>ES</i>	17.2	16.9	21.1	24.2	0.1	0.1	100	100
<i>DE</i>	19.4	17.4	21.5	24.8	0.2	0.2	100	100
<i>CH</i>	17.7	16.9	23.8	23.8	0.0	0.0	100	100
<i>Base</i>	1658	1361	2166	2006	5	5	9598	8318

Source: Own elaboration based on Verian Weighting Strategy Report.

Table 3.A.3 Unweighted and weighted distribution by Education

	<i>ISCED-02 %</i>		<i>ISCED 3-4 %</i>		<i>ISCED 5-8 %</i>		<i>Missing %</i>		<i>Total</i>	
	<i>Unw.</i>	<i>WgtMain</i>	<i>Unw.</i>	<i>WgtMain</i>	<i>Unw.</i>	<i>WgtMain</i>	<i>Unw</i>	<i>WgtMain</i>	<i>Unw</i>	<i>Wgt</i>
<i>UK</i>	26.5	19.9	18.3	38.0	55.2	42.0	0.0	0.1	100	100
<i>DK</i>	14.9	23.5	34.0	41.3	50.7	34.9	0.3	0.3	100	100
<i>HU</i>	5.9	16.4	49.7	57.9	44.4	25.7	0.0	0.0	100	100
<i>ES</i>	21.0	42.8	31.6	23.2	47.4	33.9	0.1	0.1	100	100
<i>DE</i>	3.2	6.6	41.2	59.2	55.6	34.2	0.0	0.0	100	100
<i>CH</i>	3.5	14.0	36.2	45.7	59.5	39.4	0.7	0.9	100	100
<i>Base</i>	1315	1767	3248	3586	5020	2952	15	14	9598	3819

Source: Own elaboration based on Verian Weighting Strategy Report.

4. ANNOTATED APPENDED DATABASE

The UNTWIST appended database is the result of the merge between the database at the individual level with another database with information at a higher level, in this case, the countries. To perform this type of operation we use the stata 15 command [m:1]. The linking variable, common in both databases, was the country identifier (hcountry). The merging, in this case, link perfectly [_merge == 3], there were not problems of non-response or coding errors.

The appended variables' description, measurement scale, codes and sources are detailed below:

PRESENCE OF RWPPS

Variable name: rwpp_gov

Description: Presence of a Right-Wing Populist Party in the coalition government, taking as reference the last national/federal/general elections of each polity.

Code:

- 1. Yes
- 0. No

Source: Own elaboration based on data from Parlgov (version 07/2023) (www.parlgov.org/), PolitPro (www.politpro.eu/en) and official parliamentary websites of each country.

STRENGTH OF RWPPS

Variable name: rwpp_str

Description: Strength of the RWPP in the Parliament

Measurement: seat share (%) calculated over the total number of seats of each parliament (low chamber), taking as reference the last national/federal/general elections of each polity.

Denmark (Elections 2022). Total seats: 179

- Dansk Folkeparti (Danish People's Party): 5
- Nye Borgerlige (The New Right): 6
- Danmarksdemokraterne (Denmark Democrats): 14

Hungary (Elections 2022). Total seats: 199

- Fidez: 117

Spain (Elections 2023). Total seats: 350

- Vox: 33

Germany (Elections 2021). Total seats: 736

- AfD (Alternative für Deutschland/Alternative for Germany): 83

Switzerland (Elections 2023). Total seats: 200

- SVP/UDS (Swiss People's Party/Democratic Union of the Centre): 62
- EDU/UDF (Union Démocratique Fédérale/ Eidgenössisch-Demokratische Union): 2
- Lega dei Ticinesi (Lega): 1

United Kingdom (Elections 2024). Total seats: 650

- Reform UK: 5

Source: Own elaboration based on data from ParlGov (version 07/2023) (www.parl.gov.org/), PolitPro (www.politpro.eu/en) and official parliamentary websites of each country

GENDER EQUALITY

Items: `gender_eq_eu`, `gender_eq_un`, `women_econ`

Variable name: `gender_eq_eu`

Description: The Gender Equality Index is a comprehensive measure for monitoring progress in gender equality across the EU over time. It measures gender gaps and takes into account the context and different levels of achievement of Member States across a range of relevant policy areas. It shows the different outcomes of EU and national policies for women and men and contributes to the development and implementation of evidence-based policymaking in

the area of gender equality. (<https://eige.europa.eu/publications-resources/publications/gender-equality-index-2017-methodological-report>)

Measurement: The Gender Equality Index gives the EU and the Member States a score from 1 to 100. A score of 100 would mean that a country had reached full equality between women and men.

The variable shows the scores of the 2024 Index (which comes from 2022 data) for Denmark, Germany, Hungary and Spain. The most updated score for UK is from the Gender Equality Index 2020. Data is not available for Switzerland.

Source: European Institute for Gender Equality (<https://eige.europa.eu/gender-equality-index/2024>).

Variable name: gender_eq_un

Description: Gender Inequality Index 2022 (GII). GII is a composite metric of gender inequality using three dimensions: reproductive health, empowerment and the labour market. A low GII value indicates low inequality between women and men, and vice-versa. It shows the loss in potential human development due to inequality between female and male achievements in these dimensions.

Measurement: It ranges from 0, where women and men fare equally, to 1, where one gender fares as poorly as possible in all measured dimensions. (<https://hdr.undp.org/data-center/thematic-composite-indices/gender-inequality-index#/indicies/GII>)

Source: United Nations Development Programme (<https://hdr.undp.org/>)

Variable name: women_econ

Description: Women Business and Law Index Score The index measures how laws and regulations affect women's economic opportunity. Overall scores are calculated by taking the average score of each index (Mobility, Workplace, Pay, Marriage, Parenthood, Entrepreneurship, Assets and Pension).

Measurement: Scale goes from 1 to 100, with 100 representing the highest possible score.

Source: World Bank (https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SG.LAW.INDX?locations=ES-DE-DK-CH-HU-GB&name_desc=false)

MIGRATION

Variable name: net_migrationrate

Description: Net migration 2023 is the net total of migrants during the period, that is, the number of immigrants minus the number of emigrants, including both citizens and noncitizens.

Measurement: It is measured in millions of people.

Source: World Bank (<https://data.worldbank.org/>)

GROSS DOMESTIC PRODUCT GROWTH (ANNUAL %) 2023

Variable name: gdp_growth

Description: Annual percentage growth rate of GDP at market prices based on constant local currency. GDP is the sum of gross value added by all resident producers in the economy plus any product taxes and minus any subsidies not included in the value of the products. It is calculated without making deductions for depreciation of fabricated assets or for depletion and degradation of natural resources.

The United Nations System of National Accounts calls for value added to be valued at either basic prices (excluding net taxes on products) or producer prices (including net taxes on products paid by producers but excluding sales or value added taxes). Both valuations exclude transport charges that are invoiced separately by producers. Total GDP is measured at purchaser prices. Value added by industry is normally measured at basic prices. When value added is measured at producer prices.

Measurement: Annual percentage growth rate of GDP at market prices based on constant local currency (weighted average). Aggregates are based on constant 2015 prices, expressed in U.S. dollars.

Source: World Bank national accounts data, and OECD National Accounts data files (<https://data.worldbank.org/>).

HUMAN DEVELOPMENT INDEX (HDI 2022)

Variable name: hdi

Description: The Human Development Index (HDI) is a summary measure of average achievement in key dimensions of human development: a long and healthy life, being knowledgeable and having a decent standard of living.

Measurement: The HDI is the geometric mean of normalized indices for each of the three dimensions.

Low (< 0.550)

Medium (0.550-0.699)

High (0.700-0.799)

Very high (\geq 0.800)

Source: United Nations Development Programme (<https://hdr.undp.org/>)

5. UNTWIST CODEBOOK

5.1 Main individual data variables

5.1.1 Mandatory – Administrative variables

Items: comp_Incomplete, comp_Completed, isdesktop, istouch, istable, isgeneric, ismobile, qosno

comp_Incomplete

1 Incomplete interview

comp_Completed

1 Completed interview

isdesktop - Completed on desktop (PC/Mac)

0 No

1 Yes

istouch - Completed on touch device

0 No

1 Yes

istablet - Completed on tablet

0 No

1 Yes

isgeneric - Completed on generic mobil

0 No

1 Yes

ismobile - Completed on mobile

0 No

1 Yes

qosno - Operating System version number

6 Windows NT

10 Windows 7

13 Android

16 Macintosh

18 Iphone

19 Ipad

25 Unknown

5.1.2 Identifier and weight variables

Items: userid, language, I_ch, hcountry, q0 (UK), hversion, WgtMain, WgtMainBoost, Educ, Agegp, rwpp_gender, ES_region, HU_region

userid

Type: Numeric (integer)

Concept: Respondent's identification number

Question: UserID

Sample

Type: Code

Concept: fieldwork membership

1 Main

2 Boost

language - language

Type: Code

6 Danish

7 German

9 English

10 Spanish

14 Hungarian

2055 German (Switzerland)

2064 Italian (Switzerland)

4108 French (Switzerland)

I_ch

Type: Code

Concept: language questionnaire for Switzerland

Question: Please, indicate in which language do you prefer to respond.

2055 German (Switzerland)

2064 Italian (Switzerland)

4108 French (Switzerland)

hcountry

Type: Code

Concept: geographic country

Question: Choose your country

- 1 UK
- 2 Denmark
- 3 Hungary
- 4 Spain
- 5 Germany
- 6 Switzerland

q0 (UK)

Type: Code

Concept: British citizenship

Question: Are you a British citizen?

- 1 Yes
- 2 No
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't know)

hversion

Type: Code

Concept: fieldwork belonging

- 1 PILOT
- 2 MAIN

WgtMain

Type: Numeric (decimal), Weight

Concept: Final post stratification weight - main sample (Sex, Age group, Education, and Region)

WgtMainBoost

Type: Numeric (decimal), Weight

Concept: Final post stratification weight - main sample (Sex, Age group, Education, Region, and RWPP voters by gender)

Educ

Type: Code, Weight

Concept: Education group for weighting

- 1 ISCED 0-2
- 2 ISCED 3-4
- 3 ISCED 5-8

agegp

Type: Code, Weight

Concept: age groups for weighting

- 1 18-24
- 2 35-39
- 3 40-54
- 4 55-64
- 5 65+

rwpp_gender

Type: Code, Weight

Concept: propensity to vote RWPPs by gender for weighting

- 1 Men: Score 8-10
- 2 Women: Score 8-10
- 3 Men: Score 0-7 or DK
- 4 Women: Score 0-7 or DK
- 5 Missing: Score 8-10
- 6 Missing: Score 0-7 or DK

ES_region

Type: Code, Weight

Concept: region for weighting - Spain

- 1 Noroeste
- 2 Noreste
- 3 Comunidad de Madrid
- 4 Centro (ES)
- 5 Este
- 6 Sur

7 Canarias

HU_region

Type: Code, Weight

Concept: region for weighting - Hungary

11 Budapest

12 Pest

21 Közép-Dunántúl

22 Nyugat-Dunántúl

23 Dél-Dunántúl

31 Észak-Magyarország

32 Észak-Alföld

33 Dél-Alföld

5.1.3 Values and attitudes

Items: q6, q7, q8, q9, q10, q11, q12, q13, q14, q15, q16, q17, q19, q20, q21, q22, q23, q55

q6

Items: q6_1 - q6_16, q6_888, q6_999, q6_uk, q6_dk, q6_es, q6_de, q6_ch

Type: Code

Concept: General perception of discrimination

Question: Do you think any of these groups experience disadvantages in [COUNTRY]?

q6_1 - q6_16: harmonized version of q6

q6_1

Men

q6_2

Women

q6_3

Younger people

q6_4

Older people

q6_5

LGBTQ+ people

q6_6

Heterosexual people

q6_7

Refugees/Immigrants

q6_8

Working class people

q6_9

Middle class people

q6_10

Upper class people

q6_11

Religious minorities

q6_12

Religious majorities

q6_13

Non-disabled people

q6_14

Disabled people

q6_15

Ethnic minorities

q6_16

Other (Zsidók-Jews-HU)

q6_888

Refusal

q6_999

Don't Know

q6_uk

q6_uk_1 Men

q6_uk_2 Women

q6_uk_3 Younger people

q6_uk_4 Older people

q6_uk_5 LGBTQ+ people

q6_uk_6 Heterosexual people

q6_uk_7 Refugees/Immigrants

q6_uk_8 Working class people

q6_uk_9	Middle class people
q6_uk_10	Upper class people
q6_uk_11	British religious minorities (Muslims, Jews, Hindus, Sikhs, Buddhists, Other)
q6_uk_12	British religious majorities (Christians)
q6_uk_13	Non-disabled people
q6_uk_14	Disabled people
q6_uk_15	Ethnic minorities (i.e. those who are not White British)
q6_uk_888	(Refusal)
q6_uk_999	(Don't Know)

d6_dk

q6_dk_1	Mænd
q6_dk_2	Kvinder
q6_dk_3	Yngre
q6_dk_4	Ældre
q6_dk_5	LGBTI+ personer
q6_dk_6	Heteroseksuelle
q6_dk_7	Flygtninge/Immigranter
q6_dk_8	Arbejderklassen
q6_dk_9	Middelklassen
q6_dk_10	Overklassen
q6_dk_11	Religiøse minoriteter (f.eks. muslimer, jøder, katolikker)
q6_dk_12	Protestanter (f.eks. Den danske folkekirke)
q6_dk_13	Personer uden handicap
q6_dk_14	Personer med handicap
q6_dk_15	Grønlandere/ Færinger
q6_dk_888	(Refusal)
q6_dk_999	(Don't Know)

q6_hu

q6_hu_1	Férfiak
q6_hu_2	Nők
q6_hu_3	Fiatalok
q6_hu_4	Idősek
q6_hu_5	LMBTI+ emberek

q6_hu_6	Heteroszexuális emberek
q6_hu_7	Menekültek/Bevándorlók
q6_hu_8	Munkásosztálybeliek
q6_hu_9	Középosztálybeliek
q6_hu_10	Felsőbb osztálybeliek
q6_hu_11	HUNGARY Vallási kisebbségi felekezetek (izraelita, Hit Gyülekezete, baptisták stb.)
q6_hu_12	HUNGARY Vallási többségi felekezetek (római katolikus, református, evangélikus)
q6_hu_13	Éptestű emberek
q6_hu_14	Fogyatékkal élők
q6_hu_15	Etnikai kisebbségek (pl. romák)
q6_hu_16	Zsidók
q6_hu_888	(Refusal)
q6_hu_999	(Don't Know)

q6_es

q6_es_1	Hombres
q6_es_2	Mujeres
q6_es_3	Jóvenes
q6_es_4	Mayores
q6_es_5	Personas LGTBI+
q6_es_6	Personas heterosexuales
q6_es_7	Personas refugiadas/inmigrantes
q6_es_8	Clases trabajadoras
q6_es_9	Clases medias
q6_es_10	Clases altas
q6_es_11	Minorías religiosas en España (Musulmanes, evangélicos, ortodoxos, judíos)
q6_es_12	Mayorías religiosas en España (Cristianos católicos)
q6_es_13	Personas sin discapacidad
q6_es_14	Personas con discapacidad
q6_es_15	Personas gitanas
q6_es_888	(Refusal)
q6_es_999	(Don't Know)

q6_de

q6_de_1	Männer
q6_de_2	Frauen
q6_de_3	Jüngere Menschen
q6_de_4	Ältere Menschen
q6_de_5	LGTBI+ Menschen
q6_de_6	Heterosexuelle Menschen
q6_de_7	Flüchtlinge/Immigranten
q6_de_8	Menschen der Unterschicht
q6_de_9	Mittelschicht
q6_de_10	Oberschicht
q6_de_11	Muslime
q6_de_12	Katholiken und Protestanten
q6_de_13	Nicht-behinderte Menschen
q6_de_14	Behinderte Menschen
q6_de_15	Sinti und Roma
q6_de_888	(Refusal)
q6_de_999	(Don't Know)

q6_ch

q6_ch_1	Les hommes
q6_ch_2	Les femmes
q6_ch_3	Les jeunes
q6_ch_4	Les personnes âgées
q6_ch_5	Les personnes LGTBI
q6_ch_6	Les personnes hétérosexuelles
q6_ch_7	Les réfugié.e.s/Les immigrantes
q6_ch_8	Les classes populaires
q6_ch_9	Les classes moyennes
q6_ch_10	Les classes supérieures
q6_ch_11	Minorités religieuses suisses (Les Musulmans / Les Juifs)
q6_ch_12	Les Chrétiens
q6_ch_13	Les personnes sans handicap
q6_ch_14	Les personnes avec handicap
q6_ch_15	Les Roms/les Sinti

q6_ch_888 (Refusal)
q6_ch_999 (Don't Know)

q7

Type: Code

Concept: Interest in politics

Question: How interested would you say you are in politics? Are you...

- 1 Very interested
- 2 Quite interested
- 3 Hardly interested
- 4 Not at all interested
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't know)

q8

Type: Code

Concept: Getting political information

Question: On a typical day, about how much time do you dedicate to consuming news related to politics and current affairs? This includes watching, reading, or listening through various mediums such as TV, radio, newspapers, or social

- 1 No time at all
- 2 Less than 0,5 hour
- 3 0,5 hour to 1 hour
- 4 More than 1 hour, up to 1,5 hours
- 5 More than 1,5 hours, up to 2 hours
- 6 More than 2 hours, up to 2,5 hours
- 7 More than 2,5 hours, up to 3 hours
- 8 More than 3 hours
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't know)

q9

Type: Code

Concept: Political competence

Question: How difficult or easy do you find it to make your mind up about political issues?

- 1 Very difficult
- 2 Difficult
- 3 Neither difficult nor easy
- 4 Easy
- 5 Very easy
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't know)

q10

Type: Code

Concept: Political efficacy I

Question: How much would you say the political system in [COUNTRY] allows people like you to have a say in what the government does?

- 1 Not at all
- 2 Very little
- 3 Some
- 4 A lot
- 5 A great deal
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't know)

q11

Type: Code

Concept: Political efficacy II

Question: How much would you say that politicians care what people like you think?

- 1 Hardly any politicians care
- 2 Very few care
- 3 Some care
- 4 Many care
- 5 Most politicians care
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't know)

q12

Type: Code

Concept: Strong leaders bend rules

Question: Having a strong leader in government is good for [COUNTRY] even if the leader bends the rules to get things done.

- 0 0 Totally disagree
- 1 1
- 2 2
- 3 3
- 4 4
- 5 5
- 6 6
- 7 7
- 8 8
- 9 9
- 10 10 Totally agree
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't know)

q13

Type: Code

Concept: Living in a democratic country

Question: How important is it for you to live in a country that is governed democratically?

- 0 0 Not at all important
- 1 1
- 2 2
- 3 3
- 4 4
- 5 5
- 6 6
- 7 7
- 8 8
- 9 9
- 10 10 Extremely important
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't know)

q14

Items: q14_1- q14_6

Type: Code

Concept: Political and institutional trust

Question: Please tell me on a scale of 0-10 how much you personally trust each of the following institutions. 0 means you do not trust an institution at all, and 10 means you have complete trust.

0	0 No trust at all
1	1
2	2
3	3
4	4
5	5
6	6
7	7
8	8
9	9
10	10 Complete trust
888	(Refusal)
999	(Don't know)

q14_1

Legal system

q14_2

Parliament

q14_3

Government

q14_4

Political parties

q14_5

Civil servants

q14_6

Police

q15

Type: Code

Concept: Satisfaction with democracy

Question: On the whole, how satisfied are you with the way democracy works in the [CONTRY]? 0 means that you are totally dissatisfied and 10 means that you are totally satisfied.

- | | |
|-----|------------------------|
| 0 | 0 Totally dissatisfied |
| 1 | 1 |
| 2 | 2 |
| 3 | 3 |
| 4 | 4 |
| 5 | 5 |
| 6 | 6 |
| 7 | 7 |
| 8 | 8 |
| 9 | 9 |
| 10 | 10 Totally satisfied |
| 888 | (Refusal) |
| 999 | (Don't know) |

q16

Items: q16_1- q16_7

Type: Code

Concept: MOSAiCH (Measurement and Observation of Social Attitudes in Switzerland) – ISSP identities

Question: We all belong to different groups. Yet, there are groups that are of more importance to us than others. How important are the following characteristics to you when you want to describe who you are? Please answer using the following scale from 0 to 10, where 0 means the characteristic is not important at all, and 10 means it is extremely important.

- | | |
|----|------------------------|
| 0 | 0 Not at all important |
| 1 | 1 |
| 2 | 2 |
| 3 | 3 |
| 4 | 4 |
| 5 | 5 |
| 6 | 6 |
| 7 | 7 |
| 8 | 8 |
| 9 | 9 |
| 10 | 10 Extremely important |

888 (Refusal)

999 (Don't know)

q16_1

My sex

q16_2

My religion or belief (including being agnostic or atheist)

q16_3

My nationality

q16_4

My social class (upper, middle, working class, etc.)

q16_5

My age

q16_6

My sexual orientation (heterosexual, gay, lesbian, bisexual, etc.)

q16_7

My race or ethnic origin

q17

Type: Code

Concept: Attitudes toward gender equality

Question: Do you think that equality between men and women has been achieved in [COUNTRY]?

1 Yes, definitely

2 Yes, to some extent

3 No, not really

4 No, not at all

888 (Refusal)

999 (Don't know)

q18

Items: q18_1- q18_na_999

Type: Code

Concept: Attitudes towards feminism and LGBTQI+ rights discourses

Question: For the following movements or social organizations, please tell me what degree of sympathy you have towards each of them. Use this scale from 0 to 10, where 0 means 'no sympathy at all' and 10 means 'a lot of sympathy'.

- 0 0 No sympathy at all
- 1 1
- 2 2
- 3 3
- 4 4
- 5 5
- 6 6
- 7 7
- 8 8
- 9 9
- 10 10 A lot of sympathy
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't know)

q18_1

Feminist/women's rights organisations

q18_2

Gay and lesbian organisations

q18_na_888

(Refusal)

q18_na_999

(Don't Know)

q19

Items: q19_1- q19_na_999

Type: Code

Concept: Attitudes towards equal opportunities

Question: Do you think attempts to give equal opportunities have gone too far or not gone far enough for:

- 1 Gone much too far
- 2 Gone too far
- 3 About right
- 4 Not gone far enough
- 5 Not gone nearly far enough
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't know)

q19_1

Women

19_2

Lesbian, gay and bisexual people

19_3

Transgender people

q19_na_888

(Refusal)

q19_na_999

(Don't Know)

q20

Type: Code

Concept: Attitudes toward division of labour I

Question: People have different opinions about how well mothers and fathers are suited to look after their children. Which of the following statements comes closest to your opinion?

- 1 Mothers are much better suited
- 2 Mothers are somewhat better suited
- 3 Mothers and fathers are equally suited
- 4 Fathers are somewhat better suited
- 5 Fathers are much better suited

888 (Refusal)

999 (Don't know)

q21

Type: Code

Concept: Attitudes toward division of labour II

Question: To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statement on the changing roles of men and women today? Both men and women should contribute to the household income.

- 1 Strongly agree
- 2 Agree
- 3 Neither agree nor disagree
- 4 Disagree
- 5 Strongly disagree

888 (Refusal)

999 (Don't know)

q22

Type: Code

Concept: Labour market discrimination I

Question: To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statement?
Choose your answer between 0 and 10, where 0 means you totally disagree and 10 means you totally agree.

When jobs are scarce, employers should give priority to people of the country of origin rather than immigrants.

0 0 Totally disagree

1 1

2 2

3 3

4 4

5 5

6 6

7 7

8 8

9 9

10 10 Totally agree

888 (Refusal)

999 (Don't know)

q23

Type: Code

Concept: Labour market discrimination II

Question: To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statement?
Choose your answer between 0 and 10, where 0 means you totally disagree and 10 means you totally agree.

When jobs are scarce, men should have more right to a job than women.

0 0 Totally disagree

1 1

2 2

3 3

4 4

5 5

6 6

7	7
8	8
9	9
10	10 Totally agree
888	(Refusal)
999	(Don't know)

q55

Type: Code

Concept: Ideological self-placement

Question: In politics, people sometimes talk of the 'left' and the 'right'. Where would you place yourself on this scale, where 0 means left and 10 means right?

0	0 Left
1	1
2	2
3	3
4	4
5	5
6	6
7	7
8	8
9	9
10	10 Right
888	(Refusal)
999	(Don't Know)

5.1.4 Gendered relative deprivation

Items: q24, q25, q26, q27, q28, q29, q30, q31, q32, q33, q34, q35, q36, q37, q38, q39, q40.

q24

Type: Code

Concept: Collective gender identity intersected with social class

Question: Everyone faces different situations and problems in their everyday lives. When you think of people like you, which of the following groups face situations and problems more similar to yours?

- 1 Men from your same social class
- 2 Women from your same social class
- 3 All people (men and women) from your same social class
- 4 Neither. Your problems are different from those of people in your same social class
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't know)

q25

Type: Code

Concept: Collective gender identity intersected with age

Question: Everyone faces different situations and problems in their everyday lives. When you think of people like you, which of the following groups face situations and problems more similar to yours?

- 1 Men your same age
- 2 Women your same age
- 3 All people (men and women) your same age
- 4 Neither. Your problems are different from those of people your age.
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't know)

q26

Type: Code

Concept: Collective gender identity intersected with ethnic origin

Question: Everyone faces different situations and problems in their everyday lives. When you think of people like you, which of the following groups face situations and problems more similar to yours?

- 1 Men from your same ethnic origin
- 2 Women from your same ethnic origin
- 3 All people (men and women) from your same ethnic origin
- 4 Neither. Your problems are different from those of people from your same ethnic origin.
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't know)

q27

Type: Code

Concept: Collective gender identity intersected with religious confession

Question: Everyone faces different situations and problems in their everyday lives. When you think of people like you, which of the following groups face situations and problems more similar to yours.

- 1 Men from your same religion
 - 2 Women from your same religion.
 - 3 All people (men and women) from your same religion.
 - 4 Neither. Your problems are different from those of people from your same religion.
- 888 (Refusal)
999 (Don't know)

q28

Type: Code

Concept: Collective gender identity intersected with sexuality

Question: Everyone faces different situations and problems in their everyday lives. When you think of people like you, which of the following groups face situations and problems more similar to yours?

- 1 Men with your same sexual orientation
 - 2 Women with your same sexual orientation
 - 3 All people (men and women) with your same sexual orientation
 - 4 Neither. Your problems are different from those of people with your same sexual orientation.
- 888 (Refusal)
999 (Don't know)

q29

Type: Code

Concept: Collective gender identity intersected with nationality

Question: Everyone faces different situations and problems in their everyday lives. When you think of people like you, which of the following groups face situations and problems more similar to yours?

- 1 British men
- 2 British women
- 3 All your fellow British people (men and women)
- 4 Neither. Your problems are different from those of fellow British people

- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't know)

q30

Type: Code

Concept: RD longitudinal past – cognitive dimension

Question: If you think about the lives of people like you in the past 20 to 30 years, which of these statements best represents your thoughts?

- 1 Life was better for people like me in the past
- 2 Life was about the same for people like me in the past
- 3 Life was worse for people like me in the past
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't know)

q31

Type: Code

Concept: RD longitudinal past – affective dimension

Question: And how does this make you feel?

- 1 Depressed
- 2 Angry
- 3 Content
- 4 Excited
- 5 Other (TYPE IN):
- 6 Indifferent
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't know)

q32

Type: Code

Concept: RD longitudinal future – cognitive dimension

Question: Now, if you think about what the future will be like for people like you in 20 to 30 years, which of these statements best represents your thoughts?

- 1 Life will be better for people like me in the future
- 2 Life will be about the same for people like me in the future
- 3 Life will be worse for people like me in the future
- 888 (Refusal)

999 (Don't know)

q33

Type: Code

Concept: RD longitudinal future – affective dimension

Question: And how does this make you feel?

- 1 Depressed
- 2 Angry
- 3 Indifferent
- 4 Excited
- 5 Other (TYPE IN):
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't know)

q34

Items: q34_1- q34_16, q34_888, q34_999, q34_uk, q34_dk, q34_hu, q34_es, q34_de, q34_ch

Type: Code

Concept: RD relational comparison – cognitive and affective dimension

Question: Do you think any of these groups have unfair advantages in our society compared to people like you?

q34_1 - q34_16: harmonized version of q34

q34_1

Men

q34_2

Women

q34_3

Younger people

q34_4

Older people

q34_5

LGBTQ+ people

q34_6

Heterosexual people

q34_7

Refugees/Immigrants

q34_8

Working class people

q34_9

Middle class people

q34_10

Upper class people

q34_11

Religious minorities

q34_12

Religious majorities

q34_13

Non-disabled people

q34_14

Disabled people

q34_15

Ethnic minorities

q34_16

Other (Zsidók-Jews-HU)

q34_888

Refusal

q34_999

Don't Know

q34_uk

q34_uk_1 Men

q34_uk_2 Women

q34_uk_3 Younger people

q34_uk_4 Older people

q34_uk_5 LGBTQ+ people

q34_uk_6 Heterosexual people

q34_uk_7 Refugees/Immigrants

q34_uk_8 Working class people

q34_uk_9 Middle class people

q34_uk_10 Upper class people

q34_uk_11	British religious minorities (Muslims, Jews, Hindus, Sikhs, Buddhists, Other)
q34_uk_12	British religious majorities (Christians)
q34_uk_13	Non-disabled people
q34_uk_14	Disabled people
q34_uk_15	Ethnic minorities (i.e. those who are not White British)
q34_uk_888	Refusal
q34_uk_999	Don't Know

q34_dk

q34_dk_1	Mænd
q34_dk_2	Kvinder
q34_dk_3	Yngre
q34_dk_4	Ældre
q34_dk_5	LGBTI+ personer
q34_dk_6	Heteroseksuelle
q34_dk_7	Flygtninge/Immigranter
q34_dk_8	Arbejderklassen
q34_dk_9	Middelklassen
q34_dk_10	Overklassen
q34_dk_11	Religiøse minoriteter (f.eks. muslimer, jøder, katolikker)
q34_dk_12	Protestanter (f.eks. Den danske folkekirke)
q34_dk_13	Personer uden handicap
q34_dk_14	Personer med handicap
q34_dk_15	Grønlandere/ Færinger
q34_dk_888	Refusal
q34_dk_999	Don't Know

q34_hu

q34_hu_1	Férfiak
q34_hu_2	Nők
q34_hu_3	Fiatalok
q34_hu_4	Idősek
q34_hu_5	LMBTI+ emberek
q34_hu_6	Heteroszexuális emberek
q34_hu_7	Menekültek/Bevándorlók

q34_hu_8	Munkásosztálybeliek
q34_hu_19	Középosztálybeliek
q34_hu_10	Felsőbb osztálybeliek
q34_hu_11	HUNGARY Vallási kisebbségi felekezetek (izraelita, Hit Gyülekezete, baptisták stb.)
q34_hu_12	HUNGARY Vallási többségi felekezetek (római katolikus, református, evangélikus)
q34_hu_13	Éptestű emberek
q34_hu_14	Fogyatékkal élők
q34_hu_15	Etnikai kisebbségek (pl. romák)
q34_hu_16	Zsidók
q34_hu_888	Refusal
q34_hu_999	Don't Know

q34_es

q34_es_1	Hombres
q34_es_2	Mujeres
q34_es_3	Jóvenes
q34_es_4	Mayores
q34_es_5	Personas LGTBI+
q34_es_6	Personas heterosexuales
q34_es_7	Personas refugiadas/inmigrantes
q34_es_8	Clases trabajadoras
q34_es_9	Clases medias
q34_es_10	Clases altas
q34_es_11	Minorías religiosas en España (Musulmanes, evangélicos, ortodoxos, judíos)
q34_es_12	Mayorías religiosas en España (Cristianos católicos)
q34_es_13	Personas sin discapacidad
q34_es_14	Personas con discapacidad
q34_es_15	Personas gitanas
q34_es_888	Refusal
q34_es_999	Don't Know

q34_de

q34_de_1	Männer
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q34_de_2	Frauen
q34_de_3	Jüngere Menschen
q34_de_4	Ältere Menschen
q34_de_5	LGTBI+ Menschen
q34_de_6	Heterosexuelle Menschen
q34_de_7	Flüchtlinge/Immigranten
q34_de_8	Menschen der Unterschicht
q34_de_9	Mittelschicht
q34_de_10	Oberschicht
q34_de_11	Muslime
q34_de_12	Katholiken und Protestanten
q34_de_13	Nicht-behinderte Menschen
q34_de_14	Behinderte Menschen
q34_de_15	Sinti und Roma
q34_de_888	Refusal
q34_de_999	Don't Know

q34_ch

q34_ch_1	Les hommes
q34_ch_2	Les femmes
q34_ch_3	Les jeunes
q34_ch_4	Les personnes âgées
q34_ch_5	Les personnes LGTBI
q34_ch_6	Les personnes hétérosexuelles
q34_ch_7	Les réfugiées/Les immigrantes
q34_ch_8	Les classes populaires
q34_ch_9	Les classes moyennes
q34_ch_10	Les classes supérieures
q34_ch_11	Minorités religieuses suisses (Les Musulmans / Les Juifs
q34_ch_12	Les Chrétiens
q34_ch_13	Les Juifs
q34_ch_14	Les personnes sans handicap
q34_ch_15	Les personnes avec handicap
q34_ch_16	Les Roms/les Sinti
q34_ch_888	Refusal

q34_ch_999 Don't Know

q35

Items: q35g1, q35g2, q35g3

Type: Code

Concept: Type of unfair advantage

Question: For *[PROGRAMMER: substitute the name of each group the respondent has selected in question 34 -previous one- [GROUP 1] [GROUP 2] [GROUP 3]]*, can you tell me if the unfair advantage they enjoy is related to:

q35g1 Group 1

q35g2 Group 2

q35g3 Group 3

- 1 Material / economic advantages
- 2 Legal / rights advantages
- 3 Both material/economic and legal/rights advantages
- 4 Other types of advantage. Please specify (TYPE IN):
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't know)

q36

Type: Code

Concept: Own deservingness

Question: On a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 means you totally disagree with the statement and 5 means that you totally agree with the statement, please tell me how much you agree with the following statement:

People like me are more deserving than others based on the benefits we bring to our society.

- 1 1 Totally disagree
- 2 2
- 3 3
- 4 4
- 5 5 Totally agree
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't know)

q37

Type: Code

Concept: Cultural chauvinism

Question: To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statement?
Choose your answer between 0 and 10, where 0 means you totally disagree and 10 means you totally agree.

More efforts should be made to preserve our culture and traditions instead of allowing significant cultural diversity.

0 0 Totally disagree

1 1

2 2

3 3

4 4

5 5

6 6

7 7

8 8

9 9

10 10 Totally agree

888 (Refusal)

999 (Don't know)

q38

Type: Code

Concept: Resentful anger – norms

Question: Thinking about the situations and problems that people like you face daily, which of the following has more negative impact?

1 Patriarchy

2 Feminism

3 Nationalism

4 Racism

5 None of them

888 (Refusal)

999 (Don't know)

q39

Type: Code

Concept: Resentful anger – ideologies

Question: Thinking about the situations and problems that people like you face daily, which of the following has more negative impact?

- 1 Fascism/authoritarianism
- 2 Democracy
- 3 Liberalism
- 4 Communism
- 5 Capitalism
- 6 Globalisation
- 7 Environmentalism
- 8 None of them
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't know)

q40

Type: Code

Concept: Resentful anger - institutional actors (OPTION A PRES-TEST)

Question: Thinking about the situations and problems that people like you face daily, which of the following has more negative impact?

- 1 The government
- 2 Right-wing movements
- 3 Left-wing movements
- 4 Non-governmental organisations (NGOs)
- 5 Political parties
- 6 Economic elites (multinational companies or corporations)
- 7 The European Union
- 8 Religious fundamentalism
- 9 None of them
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't know)

5.1.5 Political behaviour

Items: q5, rwpp_ptvrec, q41, q42, q43, q44, q45, q46, q47, q48

q5

Items: q5_1 – q5_59; q5_na_888

Type: Code

Concept: propensity to vote, PTV

Question: We have a number of parties in [COUNTRY], each of which would like to get your vote. How likely is it that you will ever vote for the following parties? Please answer on a scale where 0 means not at all likely and 10 means very likely.

0	0 Not at all likely
1	1
2	2
3	3
4	4
5	5
6	6
7	7
8	8
9	9
10	10 Very likely
99	Never heard about this party

q5_1

Conservative Party

q5_2

Labour Party

q5_3

Liberal Democrats

q5_4

Green Party

q5_5

United Kingdom Independence Party (UKIP)

q5_6

Reform UK (formerly the Brexit Party)

q5_7

British National Party (BNP)

q5_8

Scottish National Party (SNP)

q5_9

Plaid Cymru

q5_10

Dansk Folkeparti

q5_11

Nye Borgerlige

q5_12

Danmarksdemokraterne

q5_13

Socialdemokratiet

q5_14

Liberal Alliance

q5_15

Venstre

q5_16

Konservative

q5_17

Enhedslisten

q5_18

Socialistisk Folkeparti

q5_19

Moderaterne

q5_20

2RK Párt (Második Reformkor Párt)

q5_21

DK – MSZP - Párbeszéd - Zöldek (Demokratikus Koalíció, Magyar Szocialista Párt, Párbeszéd a Zöldek Pártja)

q5_22

FIDESZ – KDNP (Fidesz Magyar Polgári Párt, Kereszténydemokrata Néppárt)

q5_23

Jobbik (Jobbik- Konzervatívok)

q5_24

LMP – Zöldek (Magyarország Zöld Pártja)

q5_25

Mi Hazánk (Mi Hazánk Mozgalom)

q5_26

MKKP (Magyar Kétfarkú Kutya Párt)

q5_27

Momentum (Momentum Mozgalom)

q5_28

MMN (Mindenki Magyarországa Néppárt)

q5_29

TISZA (Tisztelet és Szabadság Párt)

q5_30

PP

q5_31

PSOE

q5_32

VOX

q5_33

Sumar

q5_34

Podemos

q5_35

ERC

q5_36

EAJ-PNV

q5_37

BNG

q5_38

Coalición Canaria

q5_39

Aliança Catalana

q5_40

SPD

q5_41

CDU

q5_42

Bündnis 90/Die Grünen

q5_43

FDP

q5_44

AfD

q5_45

CSU

q5_46

Die Linke

q5_47

Freie Wähler

q5_48

Tierschutzpartei

q5_49

Bündnis Sahra Wagenknecht

q5_50

UDC

q5_51

PS

q5_52

PLR

q5_53

Les Verts

q5_54

Le Centre

q5_55

PVL

q5_56

PEV

q5_57

UDF

q5_58

Lega

q5_59

Mouvement Citoyens Romand

q5_na_888

Refusal

rwpp_ptvrec

Type: Code

Concept: Recodification of propensity to vote (q5)

0 Score 0-7 or DK

1 Score 8-10

q41

Items: **q41_uk, q41_dk, q41_hu, q41_es, q41_de, q41_ch**

Type: Code

Concept: Vote recall – last election

q41_uk

Question: Which party did you vote for at the General Election in 2024?

- 1 Conservative Party
- 2 Labour Party
- 3 Liberal Democrats
- 4 Green Party
- 5 United Kingdom Independence Party (UKIP)
- 6 Brexit Party/Reform UK
- 7 British National Party (BNP)
- 8 Scottish National Party (SNP)
- 9 Plaid Cymru
- 60 Reform UK
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't know)
- 1007 Another party (TYPE IN):
- 1008 Did vote blank or null
- 1009 Did not vote
- 1010 Was not eligible to vote
- 1011 Do not remember

q41_dk

Question: Hvilket parti stemte du på ved det folketingsvalg i november 2022?

- 1 Dansk Folkeparti
- 2 Nye Borgerlige
- 3 Danmarksdemokraterne
- 4 Socialdemokratiet
- 5 Liberal Alliance
- 6 Venstre
- 7 Det Konservative Folkeparti
- 8 Enhedslisten)
- 9 Socialistisk Folkeparti
- 10 Moderaterne
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't know)
- 1007 Another party (TYPE IN):
- 1008 Did vote blank or null
- 1009 Did not vote
- 1010 Was not eligible to vote
- 1011 Do not remember

q41_hu

Question: Melyik párt listájára szavazott Ön a legutóbbi, 2022. áprilisi országgyűlési választásokon?

- 1 DK (Demokratikus Koalíció)
- 2 FIDESZ (Fidesz Magyar Polgári Párt)
- 3 Jobbik (Jobbik Magyarországért Mozgalom)
- 4 KDNP (Kereszténydemokrata Néppárt)
- 5 LMP (Lehet Más A Politika)
- 6 MEMO (Megoldás Mozgalom)
- 7 Mi Hazánk (Mi Hazánk Mozgalom)
- 8 MKKP (Magyar Kétfarkú Kutya Párt)
- 9 Momentum (Momentum Mozgalomi)
- 10 MSZP (Magyar Szocialista Párt)
- 11 Normális Párt (Normális Élet Pártja)
- 12 Párbeszéd (Párbeszéd Magyarországért Párt)
- 888 (Refusal)

- 999 (Don't know)
- 1007 Another party (TYPE IN):
- 1008 Did vote blank or null
- 1009 Did not vote
- 1010 Was not eligible to vote
- 1011 Do not remember

q41_es

Question: ¿A qué partido votó usted en las elecciones generales de julio de 2023?

- 1 PP
- 2 PSOE
- 3 VOX
- 4 Sumar
- 5 ERC
- 6 Junts x Cat
- 7 EH BILDU
- 8 EAJ-PNV
- 9 BNG
- 10 Coalición Canaria
- 11 CUP
- 12 UPN
- 13 PRC
- 14 Teruel Existe
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't know)
- 1007 Another party (TYPE IN):
- 1008 Did vote blank or null
- 1009 Did not vote
- 1010 Was not eligible to vote
- 1011 Do not remember

q41_de

Question: Welche Partei haben Sie bei der letzten Bundestagswahl im September 2021 gewählt?

- 1 SPD
- 2 CDU

- 3 Bündnis 90/Die Grünen
- 4 FDP
- 5 AfD
- 6 CSU
- 7 DIE LINKE
- 8 SSW
- 9 FREIE WÄHLER
- 10 Tierschutzpartei
- 11 dieBasis
- 12 Die PARTEI
- 13 Team Todenhöfer
- 14 PIRATEN
- 15 Volt
- 16 ÖDP
- 17 NPD
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't know)
- 1007 Another party (TYPE IN):
- 1008 Did vote blank or null
- 1009 Did not vote
- 1010 Was not eligible to vote
- 1011 Do not remember

q41_ch

Question: Pour quel(s) parti(s) avez-vous voté aux dernières élections fédérales de 2023?

- 1 Union Démocratique du Centre (UDC)
- 2 Parti socialiste (PS)
- 3 PLR.Les Libéraux-Radicaux
- 4 Les Verts (PES)
- 5 Le Centre / Parti démocrate-chrétien (PDC)
- 6 Parti vert'libéral (PVL)
- 7 Parti évangélique suisse (PEV)
- 8 Union Démocratique Fédérale (UDF)
- 9 Lega dei Ticinesi (Lega)

- 10 Parti Suisse du Travail - Parti Ouvrier et Populaire (PST-POP)
- 11 solidaritéS / Ensemble à Gauche (EàG) / Alternative Liste (AL)
- 12 Centre Gauche-PCS (CG-PCS)
- 13 Parti libéral-démocrate (LDP, Bâle)
- 14 Mouvement Citoyens Romand (MCR) - incluant MCGe et autres sections cantonales Mouvement Citoyens Romand
- 15 Parti Pirate Suisse
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't know)
- 1007 Another party (TYPE IN):
- 1008 Did vote blank or null
- 1009 Did not vote
- 1010 Was not eligible to vote
- 1011 Do not remember

q42

Items: q42_uk, q42_dk, q42_hu, q42_es, q42_de, q42_ch

Type: Code

Concept: Vote recall – previous to last elections

q42_uk

Question: Which party did you vote for at the General Election in 2019?

- 1 Conservative Party
- 2 Labour Party
- 3 Liberal Democrats
- 4 Green Party
- 5 United Kingdom Independence Party (UKIP)
- 6 Brexit Party/Reform UK
- 7 British National Party (BNP)
- 8 Scottish National Party (SNP)
- 9 Plaid Cymru
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't know)
- 1007 Another party (TYPE IN):
- 1008 Did vote blank or null
- 1009 Did not vote

- 1010 Was not eligible to vote
- 1011 Do not remember

q42_dk

Question: Hvilket parti stemte du på ved det folketingsvalg i juni 2019?

- 1 Dansk Folkeparti
- 2 Nye Borgerlige
- 3 Danmarksdemokraterne
- 4 Socialdemokratiet
- 5 Liberal Alliance
- 6 Venstre
- 7 Det Konservative Folkeparti
- 8 Enhedslisten
- 9 Socialistisk Folkeparti
- 10 Moderaterne
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't know)
- 1007 Another party (TYPE IN):
- 1008 Did vote blank or null
- 1009 Did not vote
- 1010 Was not eligible to vote
- 1011 Do not remember

q42_hu

Question: Melyik párt listájára szavazott Ön az utolsó előtti, 2018. áprilisi országgyűlési választásokon?

- 1 DK (Demokratikus Koalíció)
- 2 Együtt (Együtt – a Korszakváltók Pártja)
- 3 FIDESZ (Fidesz Magyar Polgári Párt)
- 4 Jobbik (Jobbik Magyarországért Mozgalom)
- 5 KDNP (Kereszténydemokrata Néppárt)
- 6 LMP (Lehet Más A Politika)
- 7 MIÉP (Magyar Igazság és Élet Pártja)
- 8 MKKP (Magyar Kétfarkú Kutya Párt)
- 9 Momentum (Momentum Mozgalomi)
- 10 MSZP (Magyar Szocialista Párt)

- 11 Munkáspárt (Magyar Kommunista Munkáspárt)
- 12 Párbeszéd (Párbeszéd Magyarországért Párt)
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't know)
- 1007 Another party (TYPE IN):
- 1008 Did vote blank or null
- 1009 Did not vote
- 1010 Was not eligible to vote
- 1011 Do not remember

q42_es

Question: ¿A qué partido votó usted en las elecciones generales de noviembre de 2019?

- 1 PP
- 2 PSOE
- 3 VOX
- 4 Unidas Podemos
- 5 Ciudadanos
- 6 ERC
- 7 En Comú Podem
- 8 Junts x Cat
- 9 EAJ-PNV
- 10 Más País-EQUO
- 11 EH BILDU
- 12 CUP
- 13 Més Compromís
- 14 Coalición Canaria - Nueva Canarias
- 15 BNG
- 16 Navarra Suma
- 17 PRC
- 18 Teruel Existe
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't know)
- 1007 Another party (TYPE IN):
- 1008 Did vote blank or null
- 1009 Did not vote

1010 Was not eligible to vote

1011 Do not remember

q42_de

Question: Welche Partei haben Sie bei der vorletzten Bundestagswahl im September 2017 gewählt?

1 SPD

2 CDU

3 Bündnis 90/Die Grünen

4 FDP

5 AfD

6 CSU

7 DIE LINKE

8 SSW

9 FREIE WÄHLER

10 Tierschutzpartei

11 dieBasis

12 Die PARTEI

13 Team Todenhöfer

14 PIRATEN

15 Volt

16 ÖDP

17 NPD

888 (Refusal)

999 (Don't know)

1007 Another party (TYPE IN):

1008 Did vote blank or null

1009 Did not vote

1010 Was not eligible to vote

1011 Do not remember

q42_ch

Question: Pour quel(s) parti(s) avez-vous voté aux avant-dernières élections fédérales de 2019 ?

1 Union Démocratique du Centre (UDC)

2 Parti socialiste (PS)

- 3 PLR.Les Libéraux-Radicaux
- 4 Les Verts (PES)
- 5 Le Centre / Parti démocrate-chrétien (PDC)
- 6 Parti vert'libéral (PVL)
- 7 Parti Bourgeois-Démocratique (PBD)
- 8 Parti évangélique suisse (PEV)
- 9 Union Démocratique Fédérale (UDF)
- 10 Lega dei Ticinesi (Lega)
- 11 Parti Suisse du Travail - Parti Ouvrier et Populaire (PST-POP)
- 12 solidaritéS / Ensemble à Gauche (EàG) / Alternative Liste (AL)
- 13 Centre Gauche-PCS (CG-PCS)
- 14 Mouvement Citoyens Romand (MCR) - incluant MCGe et autres sections cantonales Mouvement Citoyens Romand
- 15 Parti Pirate Suisse
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't know)
- 1007 Another party (TYPE IN):
- 1008 Did vote blank or null
- 1009 Did not vote
- 1010 Was not eligible to vote
- 1011 Do not remember

q43

Items: q43a_a_1 - q43a_a_999; q43a_b_1 - q43a_b_999;

Type: Code

Concept: Non-institutionalised political behaviours (OPTION A PRES-TEST)

Question: There are different ways of trying to improve things in **[COUNTRY]** or help prevent things from going wrong. During the last 12 months, have you done any of the following?

q43a_a_1

- 1 Contacted a politician, government, or local government official?

q43a_a_2

- 1 Participated in the activities of social, not-for-profit or charitable organisations?

q43a_a_3

- 1 Taken part in a lawful public demonstration?

q43a_a_4

1 Participated in unauthorised political rallies or protests (such as blockading streets)?

q43a_a_5

1 Posted or shared anything about politics online, for example, on blogs, via email or on social media such as Facebook or Twitter/X

q43a_a_6

1 Donated money to parties

q43a_a_777

1 None of the above

q43a_a_888

1 (Refusal)

q43a_a_999

1 (Don't Know)

Question: And, if needed in the future, would you be willing to?

q43a_b_1

1 Contact a politician, government, or local government official?

q43a_b_2

1 Participate in the activities of social, not-for-profit or charitable organisations?

q43a_b_3

1 Take part in a lawful public demonstration?

q43a_b_4

1 Participate in unauthorised political rallies or protests (such as blockading streets)?

q43a_b_5

1 Post or share anything about politics online, for example, on blogs, via email, or on social media such as Facebook or Twitter/X

q43a_b_6

1 Donate money to parties

q43a_b_777

1 None of the above

q43a_b_888

1 (Refusal)

q43a_b_999

1 (Don't Know)

Items: q43b_a_1 - q43b_a_999; q43b_b_1 - q43b_b_999;

Type: Code

Concept: Non-institutionalised political behaviours (OPTION B PRES-TEST)

Question: There are different ways of trying to improve things in **[COUNTRY]** or help prevent things from going wrong. During the last 12 months, have you done any of the following?

q43b_a_1

1 Contacted a politician, government, or local government official?

q43b_a_2

1 Participated in the activities of social, not-for-profit or charitable organisations?

q43a_a_3

1 Taken part in a lawful public demonstration?

q43a_a_4

1 Posted or shared anything about politics online, for example, on blogs, via email or on social media such as Facebook or Twitter/X

q43a_a_5

1 Donated money to parties

q43a_a_777

1 None of the above

q43a_a_888

1 (Refusal)

q43a_a_999

1 (Don't Know)

Question: And, if needed in the future, would you be willing to?

q43a_b_1

1 Contact a politician, government, or local government official?

q43a_b_2

1 Participate in the activities of social, not-for-profit or charitable organisations?

q43a_b_3

1 Take part in a lawful public demonstration?

q43a_b_4

1 Post or share anything about politics online, for example, on blogs, via email, or on social media such as Facebook or Twitter/X

q43a_b_5

1 Donate money to parties

q43a_b_777

1 None of the above

q43a_b_888

1 (Refusal)

q43a_b_999

1 (Don't Know)

q44

Items: q44_1- q44_999

Type: Code

Concept: Gendered aspiration-based preferences

Question: Here is a list of several aspects that may represent challenges for people to have the life they like and/or deserve. Please select up to five more challenging aspects for people like you.

q44_1

1 Integrating successfully into the labour market (for example, securing stable or good paid work or receiving employee be

q44_2

1 Accessing affordable housing, social services, and other goods

q44_3

1 Balancing paid employment and family duties

q44_4

1 Caring for children, elderly relatives, and other dependents

q44_5

1 Accessing good quality healthcare

q44_6

1 Getting a good education

q44_7

1 Exercising my civil rights and freedoms

q44_8

1 Being able to express my sexual orientation

q44_9

1 Being physically safe

q44_10

1 Being a good mother/father

q44_11

1 Raising and educating children

q44_12

1 Forming a family

q44_13

1 Gaining the respect of others

q44_14

1 Other. Please describe (TYPE IN):

q44_888

1 (Refusal)

q44_999

1 (Don't Know)

q45

Items: q45a, q45b

Type: Code

Concept: Closeness to parties

Question: Considering those challenging aspects you mentioned in the previous question, select the two parties that best represents your thoughts on those questions.

q45a

q45a_1

1 Conservative Party

q45a_2

1 Labour Party

q45a_3

1 Liberal Democrats

q45a_4

1 Green Party

q45a_5

1 United Kingdom Independence Party (UKIP)

q45a_6

1 Reform UK (formerly the Brexit Party)

q45a_7

1 British National Party (BNP)

q45a_8

1 Scottish National Party (SNP)

q45a_9

1 Plaid Cymru

q45a_10

1 Dansk Folkeparti

q45a_11

1 Nye Borgerlige

q45a_12

1 Danmarksdemokraterne

q45a_13

1 Socialdemokratiet

q45a_14

1 Liberal Alliance

q45a_15

1 Venstre

q45a_16

1 Konservative

q45a_17

1 Enhedslisten

q45a_18

1 Socialistisk Folkeparti

q45a_19

1 Moderaterne

q45a_20

1 2RK Párt (Második Reformkor Párt)

q45a_21

1 DK – MSZP - Párbeszéd - Zöldek (Demokratikus Koalíció, Magyar Szocialista Párt, Párbeszéd a Zöldek Pártja)

q45a_22

1 FIDESZ – KDNP (Fidesz Magyar Polgári Párt, Kereszténydemokrata Néppárt)

q45a_23

1 Jobbik (Jobbik- Konzervatívok)

q45a_24

1 LMP – Zöldek (Magyarország Zöld Pártja)

q45a_25

1 Mi Hazánk (Mi Hazánk Mozgalom)

q45a_26

1 MKKP (Magyar Kétfarkú Kutya Párt)

q45a_27

1 Momentum (Momentum Mozgalom)

q45a_28

1 MMN (Mindenki Magyarországa Néppárt)

q45a_29

1 TISZA (Tisztelet és Szabadság Párt)

q45a_30

1 PP

q45a_31

1 PSOE

q45a_32

1 VOX

q45a_33

1 Sumar

q45a_34

1 Podemos

q45a_35

1 ERC

q45a_36

1 EAJ-PNV

q45a_37

1 BNG

q45a_38

1 Coalición Canaria

q45a_39

1 Aliança Catalana

q45a_40

1 SPD

q45a_41

1 CDU

q45a_42

1 Bündnis 90/Die Grünen

q45a_43

1 FDP

q45a_44

1 AfD

q45a_45

1 CSU

q45a_46

1 Die Linke

q45a_47

1 Freie Wähler

q45a_48

1 Tierschutzpartei

q45a_49

1 Bündnis Sahra Wagenknecht

q45a_50

1 UDC

q45a_51

1 PS

q45a_52

1 PLR

q45a_53

1 Les Verts

q45a_54

1 Le Centre

q45a_55

1 PVL

q45a_56

1 PEV

q45a_57

1 UDF

q45a_58

1 Lega

q45a_59

1 Mouvement Citoyens Romand

q45a_888

1 (Refusal)

q45a_999

1 (Don't Know)

q45b

Question: How well does [PIPE PARTY FROM Q45a] represent your thoughts? Use a scale from 0 to 10, where 0 means that the party does not represent your thoughts at all, and 10 means that the party represents perfectly your thoughts.

0 0 does not represent

1 1

2 2

3 3

4 4

5 5

6 6

7 7

8 8

9 9

10 10represents perfectly

888 (Refusal)

999 (Don't know)

q46

Items: q46_1 - q46_59

Type: Code

Concept: Instrumentality – instrumental vote

Question: In your opinion, how likely are those parties that best represent your thoughts to gain representation in the parliament? Please use this scale from 0 to 10, where 0 means that the party is not likely to gain representation in parliament, and 10 means that the party is very likely to gain representation in parliament.

0 0 not likely

1 1

2 2

3 3

4 4
5 5
6 6
7 7
8 8
9 9
10 10 very likely
888 Refusal
999 Don't strength

q46_1

Conservative Party

q46_2

Labour Party

q46_3

Liberal Democrats

q46_4

Green Party

q46_5

United Kingdom Independence Party (UKIP)

q46_6

Reform UK (formerly the Brexit Party)

q46_7

British National Party (BNP)

q46_8

Scottish National Party (SNP)

q46_9

Plaid Cymru

q46_10

Dansk Folkeparti

q46_11

Nye Borgerlige

q46_12

Danmarksdemokraterne

q46_13

Socialdemokratiet

q46_14

Liberal Alliance

q46_15

Venstre

q46_16

Konservative

q46_17

Enhedslisten

q46_18

Socialistisk Folkeparti

q46_19

Moderaterne

q46_20

2RK Párt (Második Reformkor Párt)

q46_21

DK – MSZP - Párbeszéd - Zöldek (Demokratikus Koalíció, Magyar Szocialista Párt, Párbeszéd a Zöldek Pártja)

q46_22

FIDESZ – KDNP (Fidesz Magyar Polgári Párt, Kereszténydemokrata Néppárt)

q46_23

Jobbik (Jobbik- Konzervatívok)

q46_24

LMP – Zöldek (Magyarország Zöld Pártja)

q46_25

Mi Hazánk (Mi Hazánk Mozgalom)

q46_26

MKKP (Magyar Kétfarkú Kutya Párt)

q46_27

Momentum (Momentum Mozgalom)

q46_28

MMN (Mindenki Magyarországa Néppárt)

q46_29

TISZA (Tisztelet és Szabadság Párt)

q46_30

PP

q46_31

PSOE

q46_32

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q46_33

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q46_34

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q46_35

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q46_36

EAJ-PNV

q46_37

BNG

q46_38

Coalición Canaria

q46_39

Aliança Catalana

q46_40

SPD

q46_41

CDU

q46_42

Bündnis 90/Die Grünen

q46_43

FDP

q46_44

AfD

q46_45

CSU

q46_46

Die Linke

q46_47

Freie Wähler

q46_48

Tierschutzpartei

q46_49

Bündnis Sahra Wagenknecht

q46_50

UDC

q46_51

PS

q46_52

PLR

q46_53

Les Verts

q46_54

Le Centre

q46_55

PVL

q46_56

PEV

q46_57

UDF

q46_58

Lega

q46_59

Mouvement Citoyens Romand

q47

Items: q47_1 - q47_59

Type: Code

Concept: Parties strength

Question: In your opinion, how much strength-would those parties have to push policies in the direction that best represents your thoughts? Please use this scale from 0 to 10, where 0 means no strength, and 10 means a lot of strength.

0 0 No strength

1 1

2 2

3 3

4 4
5 5
6 6
7 7
8 8
9 9
10 10A lot of strength
888 Refusal
999 Don't strength

q47_1

Conservative Party

q47_2

Labour Party

q47_3

Liberal Democrats

q47_4

Green Party

q47_5

United Kingdom Independence Party (UKIP)

q47_6

Reform UK (formerly the Brexit Party)

q47_7

British National Party (BNP)

q47_8

Scottish National Party (SNP)

q47_9

Plaid Cymru

q47_10

Dansk Folkeparti

q47_11

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q47_12

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q47_13

Socialdemokratiet

q47_14

Liberal Alliance

q47_15

Venstre

q47_16

Konservative

q47_17

Enhedslisten

q47_18

Socialistisk Folkeparti

q47_19

Moderaterne

q47_20

2RK Párt (Második Reformkor Párt)

q47_21

DK – MSZP - Párbeszéd - Zöldek (Demokratikus Koalíció, Magyar Szocialista Párt, Párbeszéd a Zöldek Pártja)

q47_22

FIDESZ – KDNP (Fidesz Magyar Polgári Párt, Kereszténydemokrata Néppárt)

q47_23

Jobbik (Jobbik- Konzervatívok)

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q47_25

Mi Hazánk (Mi Hazánk Mozgalom)

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q47_27

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q47_29

TISZA (Tisztelet és Szabadság Párt)

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q47_39

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q47_40

SPD

q47_41

CDU

q47_42

Bündnis 90/Die Grünen

q47_43

FDP

q47_44

AfD

q47_45

CSU

q47_46

Die Linke

q47_47

Freie Wähler

q47_48

Tierschutzpartei

q47_49

Bündnis Sahra Wagenknecht

q47_50

UDC

q47_51

PS

q47_52

PLR

q47_53

Les Verts

q47_54

Le Centre

q47_55

PVL

q47_56

PEV

q47_57

UDF

q47_58

Lega

q47_59

Mouvement Citoyens Romand

q48

Items: q48_1 - q48_59

Type: Code

Concept: Parties credibility

Question: In your opinion, how credible are those parties to push policies in the direction that best represent your thoughts? Please use this scale from 0 to 10, where 0 means that the party is not credible, and 10 means that the party is totally credible.

0 0 Not credible at all

1 1

2 2

3 3
4 4
5 5
6 6
7 7
8 8
9 9
10 10 Totally credible
888 Refusal
999 Don't strength

q48_1

Conservative Party

q48_2

Labour Party

q48_3

Liberal Democrats

q48_4

Green Party

q48_5

United Kingdom Independence Party (UKIP)

q48_6

Reform UK (formerly the Brexit Party)

q48_7

British National Party (BNP)

q48_8

Scottish National Party (SNP)

q48_9

Plaid Cymru

q48_10

Dansk Folkeparti

q48_11

Nye Borgerlige

q48_12

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q48_13

Socialdemokratiet

q48_14

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q48_15

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q48_16

Konservative

q48_17

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q48_18

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q48_19

Moderaterne

q48_20

2RK Párt (Második Reformkor Párt)

q48_21

DK – MSZP - Párbeszéd - Zöldek (Demokratikus Koalíció, Magyar Szocialista Párt, Párbeszéd a Zöldek Pártja)

q48_22

FIDESZ – KDNP (Fidesz Magyar Polgári Párt, Kereszténydemokrata Néppárt)

q48_23

Jobbik (Jobbik- Konzervatívok)

q48_24

LMP – Zöldek (Magyarország Zöld Pártja)

q48_25

Mi Hazánk (Mi Hazánk Mozgalom)

q48_26

MKKP (Magyar Kétfarkú Kutya Párt)

q48_27

Momentum (Momentum Mozgalom)

q48_28

MMN (Mindenki Magyarországa Néppárt)

q48_29

TISZA (Tisztelet és Szabadság Párt)

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q48_49

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q48_51

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q48_57

UDF

q48_58

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q48_59

Mouvement Citoyens Romand

5.1.6 Sociodemographic

Items: q1, q2, q2recode, q3_education_harmonized, q3_uk1, q3_dk, q3_hu, q3_es, q3_de, q3_ch, q4, q49, q52_1, q53, q53_uk, q53_dk, q53_hu, q53_es, q53_de, q53_ch, q54, q56, q57, q58. q59, q60.

q1

Type: Code

Concept: Sex

Question: Are you...?

1 Male

2 Female

- 3 Other
- 4 Rather not say
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't Know)

q2

Type: Numeric (integer)

Concept: Age

Question: And in what year were you born?

q2recode

Type: Code

Concept: Recodification of q2-Age

Question: Q2: And in what year were you born?

- 1 18-24
- 2 25-39
- 3 40-54
- 4 55-64
- 5 65+
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't know)

q3_education_harmonized

Type: Code

Concept: Harmonized version of education level

- 0 Not completed ISCED level 1
- 113 ISCED 1, completed primary education
- 212 General/pre-vocational ISCED 2A/2B, access ISCED3 vocational
- 213 General ISCED 2A, access ISCED 3A general/all 3
- 222 Vocational ISCED 2A/2B, access ISCED 3 vocational
- 229 Vocational ISCED 3C < 2 years, no access ISCED 5
- 312 General ISCED 3A/3B, access ISCED 5B/lower tier 5A
- 313 General ISCED 3A, access upper tier ISCED 5A/all 5
- 321 Vocational ISCED 3C >= 2 years, no access ISCED 5
- 322 Vocational ISCED 3A/3B, access 5B/lower tier 5A

- 323 Vocational ISCED 3A, access upper tier ISCED 5A/all 5
- 413 General ISCED 4A, access upper tier ISCED 5A/all 5
- 421 ISCED 4 programmes without access ISCED 5
- 422 Vocational ISCED 4A/4B, access ISCED 5B/lower tier 5A
- 423 Vocational ISCED 4A, access upper tier ISCED 5A /all 5
- 510 ISCED 5A short, intermediate/academic/general tertiary below
- 520 ISCED 5B short, advanced vocational qualifications
- 610 ISCED 5A medium, bachelor/equivalent from lower tier tertiary
- 620 ISCED 5A medium, bachelor/equivalent from upper/single tier
- 710 ISCED 5A long, master/equivalent from lower tier tertiary
- 720 ISCED 5A long, master/equivalent from upper/single tier tertiary
- 800 ISCED 6, doctoral degree

q3_uk 1

Type: Code

Concept: Education - UK

Question: Which is the highest level of education you have successfully completed?

- 1 Ph.D, D.Phil or equivalent 1
- 2 Masters Degree, M.Phil, Post-Graduate Diplomas and Certificates
- 3 5 year University/CNAA first Degree (MB, BDS, BV etc)
- 4 3-4 year University/CNAA first Degree (BA, BSc, BEd, BEng, etc)
- 5 Nursing certificate, Teacher training
- 6 HE Diploma
- 7 Edexcel/BTEC/BEC/TEC - Higher National Diploma (HND)
- 8 OCR/RSA - Higher Diploma
- 9 City and Guilds - Level 4/Full Technological/Part IV
- 10 NVQ/SVQ Level 4 or 5 or equivalent
- 11 Foundation Degree (FdA, FdSc etc) 6
- 12 Edexcel/BTEC/BEC/TEC - Higher National Certificate (HNC) or equivalent
- 13 Certificate of Higher Education
- 14 HE Access
- 15 Vocational A-level (AVCE), GCE Applied A-level
- 16 NVQ/SVQ Level 3
- 17 GNVQ/GSVQ Advanced
- 18 Edexcel/BTEC/BEC/TEC (General/Ordinary) National Certificate or Diploma (ONC/OND)

- 19 City and Guilds Advanced (Level 3/Part III), Tech level
- 20 (Modern) Apprenticeship, Advanced (Modern) Apprenticeship
- 21 SVQ/NVQ/Key Skills Level 1 and 2
- 22 City and Guilds Craft/Intermediate (Levels 1 to 2/Parts I - II)
- 23 RSA/OCR Vocational or First Certificate/Diploma, Advanced Diploma
- 24 Edexcel/BTEC First/General Diploma, Technical Certificate,
- 25 SCOTVEC/SQA National certificate modules
- 26 2 or more A-levels, S-levels, A2-level
- 27 Scottish Highers, Scottish SCE/SLC/SUPE at Higher Grade, Scottish Higher School Certificate, Certificate of Sixth Year S
- 28 Welsh Advanced Baccalaureate
- 29 Irish Leaving Certificate
- 30 International Baccalaureate
- 31 GNVQ or GSVQ Intermediate 2
- 32 Vocational GCSE
- 33 SCOTVEC/SQA National Courses
- 34 BTEC First/General Certificate
- 35 Technical Award
- 36 5 or more GCSEs A*-C or 4-9, CSE Grade 1, GCE O-level Grades A-C or 1-6
- 37 Scottish SCE Ordinary Bands A-C or Pass, Scottish Standard Grades 1-3 or Pass
- 38 School Certificate or Matriculation
- 39 Scottish School Leaving Certificate Lower Grade, SUPE Ordinary, Scottish Intermediate 1 (A grade), Scottish Intermediate
- 40 Intermediate/National Welsh Baccalaureate
- 41 Irish Junior Certificate
- 42 1 A-level or equivalent
- 43 1-4 GCSEs A*-C or 4-9, GCSE Grades D-G or 1-3, Short course GCSE, CSE Grades 2-5, GCE O-level Grades D-E or 7-9
- 44 Scottish (SCE) Ordinary Bands D-E, Scottish Standard Grades 4-7, Scottish School Leaving Certificate - no grade, Scottish
- 45 GNVQ or GSVQ Foundation level
- 46 Foundation Welsh Baccalaureate
- 47 Skills for Life (including Basic Skills, Key Skills, Entry Level Certificates).
- 888 (Refusal)
- 997 None of these
- 999 (Don't Know)

q3_dk

Type: Code

Concept: Education - Denmark

Question: Which is the highest level of education you have successfully completed?

- 1 Ingen skolegang, Børnehaveklasse. 1.-5. klasse
- 2 Folkeskole 6.-8. klasse
- 3 9. - 10. klasse
- 4 Gymnasielle uddannelser, studentereksamen, HF, HHX, HTX
- 5 Kort erhvervsuddannelse under 1-2 års varighed, F.eks. AMU Arbejdsmarkedsuddannelser, Basisår på Erhvervsfaglige udda
- 6 Faglig uddannelse (håndværk, handel, landbrug mv.), F.eks. Faglærte, Social- og sundhedsassistent-uddannelsen og tils
- 7 Kort videregående uddannelse af op til 2-3 års varighed, F.eks. Erhvervsakademiuddannelser f.eks. datamatiker, tandple
- 8 Mellemlang videregående uddannelse af 3-4 års varighed. professionsbachelorer, F.eks. Diplomingeniør, sygeplejerske,
- 9 Universitetsbachelorer. 1. del af kandidatuddannelsen
- 10 Lang videregående uddannelse. Kandidatuddannelser af 5.-6. års varighed, F.eks. cand.mag., cand.jur., cand.polyt. etc.
- 11 Licentiat
- 12 Forskeruddannelse. Ph.d., doktor
- 13 (Andet)
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't Know)

q3_hu

Type: Code

Concept: Education - Hungary

Question: Which is the highest level of education you have successfully completed?

- 1 nem járt iskolába; 1-3 osztály általános vagy azzal egyenértékű
- 2 4-7 osztály általános vagy azzal egyenértékű
- 3 befejezett általános iskola vagy azzal egyenértékű
- 4 szakmunkásképző, szakiskola
- 5 10. évfolyamra épülő szakképzés
- 6 érettségi, befejezett szakközépiskola

- 7 érettségi, befejezett gimnázium
- 8 érettségire épülő, felsőfokra nem akkreditált szakképzés, középfokú technikum
- 9 felsőfokú akkreditált szakképzés, felsőfokú technikum
- 10 főiskolai diploma vagy főiskolai alapképzési szak – BA/BSC
- 11 egyetemi alapképzési szak – BA /BSC
- 12 főiskolai mesterképzési szak – MA/MSc
- 13 egyetemi diploma vagy egyetemi mesterképzési szak – MA/MSc
- 14 felsőfokú végzettség tudományos fokozattal
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't Know)

q3_es

Type: Code

Concept: Education - Spain

Question: Which is the highest level of education you have successfully completed?

- 1 Doctorado
- 2 Licenciatura, Máster oficial, Ingeniería Superior, Arquitectura, Título Superior en Música, Danza o Arte Dramático
- 3 Diplomatura, Grado, Ingeniería Técnica, Arquitectura Técnica, 3 años de licenciatura, Título Superior en Diseño
- 4 Peritaje, Antiguas Escuelas de Enfermería, de Magisterio o de Asistencia Social
- 5 Bachillerato (LOGSE)
- 6 PREU, COU
- 7 Bachillerato Superior, BUP
- 8 ESO (Completa)
- 9 EGB (completa)
- 10 Bachillerato Elemental
- 11 Educación primaria (Certificado de Estudios primarios, hasta 5º de EGB incluido Primaria LOGSE)
- 12 Menos de 5 años de escuela (estudios primarios sin completar)
- 13 No ha ido nunca a la escuela (sin estudios)
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't Know)

q3_de

Type: Code

Concept: Education - Germany

Question: Which is the highest level of education you have successfully completed?

- 1 Promotion oder Habilitation
- 2 Diplom, Master, Magister oder Staatsexamen einer Universität (auch Kunst-, Musik-, technische, theologische oder pädag
- 3 Master einer Fachhochschule (FH) (auch duale Hochschule)
- 4 Bachelor einer Universität (auch Kunst-, Musik-, technische, theologische oder pädagogische Hochschule)
- 5 Bachelor einer Fachhochschule (FH), Berufsakademie (auch duale Hochschule); Diplom (FH)
- 6 Diplom einer Berufsakademie (BA)
- 7 Techniker- oder gleichwertiger Fachschulabschluss (inkl. Fachschule der ehemaligen DDR); Abschluss einer Fachakademie (B
- 8 Meister
- 9 Abschluss einer Lehre (Facharbeiter-, Gesellen- oder Kaufmannsgehilfenbrief, IHK-Prüfungszeugnis)
- 10 Abschluss einer Ausbildung zum Erzieher/zur Erzieherin
- 11 Berufsqualifizierender Abschluss einer Berufsfachschule/eines Kollegs (schulische Berufsausbildung)
- 12 Abschluss einer 2- bis 3-jährigen Ausbildung an einer Schule des Gesundheitswesens (medizinische Assistenten, Gesundhei
- 13 Abschluss einer 1-jährigen Ausbildung an einer Schule des Gesundheitswesens (medizinische Hilfsberufe)
- 14 Betriebliche Anlernzeit mit Abschlusszeugnis, aber keine Lehre
- 15 Abitur, allgemeine oder fachgebundene Hochschulreife
- 16 Fachhochschulreife
- 17 Realschulabschluss, Mittlere Reife oder gleichwertiger Abschluss bzw. Polytechnische Oberschule der ehem. DDR mit Abschl
- 18 Volks- oder Hauptschulabschluss oder gleichwertiger Abschluss bzw. Polytechnische Oberschule der ehem. DDR mit Abschluss
- 19 (Noch) kein Schulabschluss, aber Grundschule (4. Klasse) beendet oder Abschluss einer Förderschule/Sonderschule
- 20 Grundschule (4. Klasse) nicht beendet
- 21 Keinen der aufgelisteten Abschlüsse
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't Know)

q3_ch

Type: Code

Concept: Education - Switzerland

Question: Which is the highest level of education you have successfully completed?

- 1 Ecole primaire inachevée
- 2 Ecole primaire (4 à 6 ans de scolarité)
- 3 Cycle d'orientation, école secondaire
- 4 10. année, préapprentissage, cours préparatoire, école préprofessionnelle
- 5 Ecoles de culture générale (3 ans, certificat d'ECG, maturité spécialisée), Ecoles de degré diplôme (EDD), Haut
- 6 Maturité gymnasiale, Gymnase, Collège
- 7 Maturité gymnasiale pour adultes ou apprentissage après maturité gymnasiale
- 8 Ecole normale, Etudes pédagogiques (niveau préscolaire et primaire)
- 9 Maturité professionnelle
- 10 Maturité professionnelle pour adultes
- 11 Formation professionnelle initiale (Attestation fédérale de formation professionnelle, Apprentissage court (2 ans), Ec
- 12 Apprentissage 3-4 ans (CFC) en entreprise formatrice ou en école professionnelle
- 13 Deuxième apprentissage ou apprentissage en tant que deuxième formation
- 14 Maîtrise professionnelle, brevet fédéral et autres examens professionnels supérieurs
- 15 Diplôme ou postgrade d'une école professionnelle supérieure, p.ex. dans les domaines techniques, administration, sant
- 16 Diplôme ou postgrade d'une des écoles supérieures suivantes : écoles d'ingénieurs ETS écoles supérieures de cadre
- 17 Hautes écoles spécialisées (HES), Hautes écoles pédagogiques (HEP): Bachelor
- 18 Hautes écoles spécialisées (HES), Hautes écoles pédagogiques (HEP): Master, diplôme, postgrade
- 19 Hautes écoles universitaires, écoles polytechniques fédérale (EPF): Demi-licence, certificat propédeutique
- 20 Hautes écoles universitaires, écoles polytechniques fédérale (EPF): Bachelor, licence en 3-4 ans
- 21 Hautes écoles universitaires, écoles polytechniques fédérale (EPF): Licence exigeant plus que 4 ans
- 22 Hautes écoles universitaires, écoles polytechniques fédérale (EPF): Master, diplôme, postgrade

- 23 Hautes écoles universitaires, écoles polytechniques fédérale (EPF): Doctorat, PhD
- 24 Autre formation (notez en détail, aussi le pays où la formation a été achevée)
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't Know)

q4

Type: Code

Concept: Size of habitat (harmonized version)

Question: Which phrase describes best the area where you live?

- 1 A big city
- 2 The suburbs or outskirts of a big city
- 3 A town or a small city
- 4 A country village
- 5 A farm or home in the countryside

q49

Type: Code

Concept: Partnership status

Question: What is your current civil partnership status?

- 1 Legally married
- 2 Legally registered civil union
- 3 Non-registered civil union (cohabitation)
- 4 Legally divorced / civil union dissolved
- 5 Separated (marriage / civil union not legally dissolved but not living with partner)
- 6 Widowed/civil partner died
- 7 Neither of these (single, never married or in civil union or cohabitation)
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't Know)

q52_1

Type: Code

Concept: Caring responsibilities

Question: On average, in a typical week, how many hours do you spend looking after family members (e.g. children, elderly, ill or disabled family members):

0	0 hours
2	1 to 4 hours
3	5 to 9 hours
4	10 to 14 hours
5	15 to 19 hours
6	20 to 24 hours
7	25 to 29 hours
8	30 to 34 hours
9	35 to 39 hours
10	40 to 44 hours
11	45 to 49 hours
12	50 to 54 hours
13	55 to 59 hours
14	60 to 64 hours
15	more than 65 hours

q53

Type: Code

Concept: Harmonized version of religious belonging

1	Roman Catholic
2	Protestant
3	Eastern Orthodox
4	Other Christian denomination
5	Jewish
6	Islam
7	Eastern religions
8	Other non-Christian religions
9	I do not consider myself to belong to any particular religion or denomina.
10	Other
777	None of the above
888	Refusal
999	Don't Know

q53_uk

Type: Code

Concept: Religious belonging - UK

Question: Do you consider yourself as belonging to any particular religion or denomination? Which one?

- 1 Roman Catholic
- 2 Church of England / Anglican
- 3 Church of Ireland
- 4 Baptist
- 5 Methodist
- 6 Presbyterian / Church of Scotland
- 7 United Reformed Church / Congregational
- 8 Free Presbyterian
- 9 Brethren
- 10 Other Protestant
- 11 Greek or Russian Orthodox
- 12 Other Eastern Orthodox
- 13 Other Christian
- 14 Hindu
- 15 Sikh
- 16 Buddhist
- 17 Other Eastern Religions
- 18 Jewish
- 19 Islam / Muslim
- 20 Other non-Christian
- 777 None of the above
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't Know)

q53_dk

Type: Code

Concept: Religious belonging - Denmark

Question: Do you consider yourself as belonging to any particular religion or denomination? Which one?

- 1 Jeg tilhører ikke en bestemt religion eller trosretning
- 2 Romersk-katolsk
- 3 Protestantisk
- 4 Østlig ortodoks

- 5 Andre kristne religioner
- 6 Jødisk
- 7 Islam
- 8 Østlige religioner
- 9 Andre ikke kristne religioner
- 777 None of the above
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't Know)

q53_hu

Type: Code

Concept: Religious belonging - Hungary

Question: Do you consider yourself as belonging to any particular religion or denomination? Which one?

- 1 Nem tartom magam egyetlen valláshoz vagy felekezethez sem tartozónak
- 2 Római katolikus
- 3 Református vagy evangélikus
- 4 Keleti ortodox
- 5 Egyéb keresztény felekezet
- 6 Zsidó
- 7 Iszlám
- 8 Keleti vallások
- 9 Egyéb nem keresztény vallás
- 777 None of the above
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't Know)

q53_es

Type: Code

Concept: Religious belonging - Spain

Question: Do you consider yourself as belonging to any particular religion or denomination? Which one?

- 1 No me considero perteneciente a ninguna religión o confesión en particular
- 2 Católica
- 3 Protestante

- 4 Ortodoxa
- 5 Otras confesiones cristianas
- 6 Judía
- 7 Musulmana
- 8 Religiones orientales (budista, hindú, sij, sintoísta, taoísta)
- 9 Otras religiones no cristianas
- 10 Otra: por favor, anote cuál
- 777 None of the above
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't Know)

q53_de

Type: Code

Concept: Religious belonging - Germany

Question: Do you consider yourself as belonging to any particular religion or denomination? Which one?

- 1 Römisch-Katholische Kirche
- 2 Evangelisch/Protestantisch Kirche (EKD, ohne Freikirche)
- 3 Evangelische Freikirche
- 4 Östlich-Orthodoxe Glaubensgemeinschaft
- 5 Andere christliche Konfession
- 6 Judentum
- 7 Muslimische Glaubensgemeinschaft/Islam
- 8 Östliche Religionsgemeinschaft (Buddhismus, Hinduismus, Sikh, Shinto, Tao etc.)
- 9 Andere nicht-christliche Religionsgemeinschaft
- 777 Nichts davon
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't Know)

q53_ch

Type: Code

Concept: Religious belonging - Switzerland

Question: Do you consider yourself as belonging to any particular religion or denomination? Which one?

- 1 Catholique

- 2 Protestante
- 3 Orthodoxe
- 4 Autre confession chrétienne
- 5 Juive
- 6 Islamique
- 7 Religions orientales
- 8 Autres religions non chrétiennes
- 9 Je ne me considère pas comme appartenant à une religion ou à une confession particulière
- 777 Aucun d'entre eux
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't Know)

q54

Type: Code

Concept: Religiosity

Question: Regardless of whether you belong to a particular religion, how religious would you say you are? Please use this scale from 0 to 10, where 0 means not at all religious, and 10 means very religious.

- 0 0 Not at all important
- 1 1
- 2 2
- 3 3
- 4 4
- 5 5
- 6 6
- 7 7
- 8 8
- 9 9
- 10 10 Very religious
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't Know)

q56

Type: Code

Concept: Employment

Question: Are you yourself gainfully employed at the moment or not? Please select the employment status that applies to you.

- 1 30 hours a week or more
- 2 Less than 30 hours a week
- 3 Self-employed
- 4 Military Service
- 5 Retired/pensioned
- 6 Housemaker not otherwise employed
- 7 Student
- 8 Unemployed
- 9 Disabled
- 10 Other, please specify (TYPE IN):
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't Know)

q57

Type: Code

Concept: Respondent's income

Question: Using this card, please tell me which letter describes your personal total income, after tax and compulsory deductions, from all sources? If you don't know the exact figure, please give an estimate.

- 1 J
- 2 R
- 3 C
- 4 M
- 5 F
- 6 S
- 7 K
- 8 P
- 9 D
- 10 H
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't Know)

United Kingdom

	Approximate WEEKLY	Approximate MONTHLY	Approximate ANNUAL	
J	Less than £288	Less than £1,233	Less than £14,800	J
R	£288 to under £333	£1,233 to under £1,425	£14,800 to under £17,100	R
C	£333 to under £375	£1,425 to under £1,608	£17,100 to under £19,300	C
M	£375 to under £421	£1,608 to under £1,808	£19,300 to under £21,700	M
F	£421 to under £476	£1,808 to under £2,042	£21,700 to under £24,500	F
S	£476 to under £546	£2,042 to under £2,341	£24,500 to under £28,100	S
K	£546 to under £640	£2,341 to under £2,742	£28,100 to under £32,900	K
P	£640 to under £777	£2,742 to under £3,333	£32,900 to under £40,000	P
D	£777 to under £992	£3,333 to under £4,250	£40,000 to under £51,000	D
H	£992 or more	£4,250 or more	£51,000 or more	H

Denmark

Din NETTOindkomst				
	Tilnærmelsesvis ugentlig	Tilnærmelsesvis månedlig	Tilnærmelsesvis årlig	
J	Mindre end 2.000 kr	Mindre end 8.000 kr	Mindre end 94.000 kr	J
R	Mellem 2.000 og 2.999 kr	Mellem 8.001 og 11.000 kr	Mellem 94.001 og 132.000 kr	R
C	Mellem 3.000 og 3.999 kr	Mellem 11.001 og 14.000 kr	Mellem 132.001 og 165.000 kr	C
M	Mellem 4.000 og 4.999 kr	Mellem 14.001 og 17.000 kr	Mellem 165.001 og 196.000 kr	M
F	Mellem 5.000 og 5.999 kr	Mellem 17.001 og 20.000 kr	Mellem 196.001 og 240.000 kr	F
S	Mellem 6.000 og 6.999 kr	Mellem 20.001 og 25.000 kr	Mellem 240.001 og 290.000 kr	S
K	Mellem 7.000 og 7.999 kr	Mellem 25.001 og 29.000 kr	Mellem 290.001 og 339.000 kr	K
P	Mellem 8.000 og 8.999 kr	Mellem 29.001 og 34.000 kr	Mellem 339.001 og 400.000 kr	P
D	Mellem 9.000 og 10.999 kr	Mellem 34.001 og 42.000 kr	Mellem 400.001 og 500.000 kr	D
H	Over 11.000 kr	Over 42.001 kr	Over 500.000 kr	H

Hungary

	Hozzávetőleges HAVI jövedelem	
J	240 ezer Ft, vagy kevesebb	J
R	240 000 – 299 999 Ft között	R
C	300 000 – 359 999 Ft között	C
M	360 000 – 409 999 Ft között	M
F	410 000 – 459 999 Ft között	F
S	460 000 – 509 999 Ft között	S
K	510 000 – 579 999 Ft között	K
P	580 000 – 659 999 Ft között	P
D	660 000 – 759 999 Ft között	D
H	760 000 Ft felett	H

Spain

	A la semana (aprox.)	Al mes (aprox.)	Al año (aprox.)	
J	180€ o menos	775€ o menos	9300€ o menos	J
R	Entre 181€ y 250€	Entre 776€ y 1100€	Entre 9301€ y 13000€	R
C	Entre 251€ y 325€	Entre 1101€ y 1400€	Entre 13001€ y 17000€	C
M	Entre 326€ y 400€	Entre 1401€ y 1700€	Entre 17001€ y 21000€	M
F	Entre 401€ y 480€	Entre 1701€ y 2000€	Entre 21001€ y 25000€	F
S	Entre 481€ y 550€	Entre 2001€ y 2400€	Entre 25001€ y 29000€	S
K	Entre 551€ y 670€	Entre 2401€ y 2900€	Entre 29001€ y 35000€	K
P	Entre 671€ y 825€	Entre 2901€ y 3500€	Entre 35001€ y 43000€	P
D	Entre 826€ y 1050€	Entre 3501€ y 4500€	Entre 43001€ y 55000€	D
H	Más de 1050€	Más de 4500€	Más de 55000€	H

Germany

	Wöchentlich (ungefähr)	Monatlich (ungefähr)	Jährlich (ungefähr)	
J	bis 260 Euro	bis 1.130 Euro	bis 13.500 Euro	J
R	261 bis 370 Euro	1.131 bis 1.610 Euro	13.501 bis 19.330 Euro	R
C	371 bis 470 Euro	1.611 bis 2.030 Euro	19.331 bis 24.350 Euro	C
M	471 bis 560 Euro	2.031 bis 2.440 Euro	24.351 bis 29.240 Euro	M
F	561 bis 670 Euro	2.441 bis 2.890 Euro	29.241 bis 34.720 Euro	F
S	671 bis 780 Euro	2.891 bis 3.390 Euro	34.721 bis 40.690 Euro	S
K	781 bis 920 Euro	3.391 bis 3.980 Euro	40.691 bis 47.710 Euro	K
P	921 bis 1.100 Euro	3.981 bis 4.750 Euro	47.711 bis 56.940 Euro	P
D	1.101 bis 1.390 Euro	4.751 bis 6.020 Euro	56.941 bis 72.220 Euro	D
H	1.391 Euro oder mehr	6.021 Euro oder mehr	72.221 Euro oder mehr	H

Switzerland

	Approximation HEBDOMADAIRE	Approximation MENSUEL	Approximation ANNUEL	
J	Moins de CHF 750	Moins de CHF 3'300	Moins de CHF 39'500	J
R	De CHF 750 à CHF 1'000	De CHF 3'300 à CHF 4'300	De CHF 39'500 à CHF 52'000	R
C	De CHF 1'000 à CHF 1'250	De CHF 4'300 à CHF 5'400	De CHF 52'000 à CHF 65'000	C
M	De CHF 1'250 à CHF 1'500	De CHF 5'400 à CHF 6'500	De CHF 65'000 à CHF 78'000	M
F	De CHF 1'500 à CHF 1'750	De CHF 6'500 à CHF 7'600	De CHF 78'000 à CHF 91'500	F
S	De CHF 1'750 à CHF 2'050	De CHF 7'600 à CHF 8'900	De CHF 91'500 à CHF 106'000	S
K	De CHF 2'050 à CHF 2'400	De CHF 8'900 à CHF 10'400	De CHF 106'000 à CHF 125'000	K
P	De CHF 2'400 à CHF 2'850	De CHF 10'400 à CHF 12'400	De CHF 125'000 à CHF 148'500	P
D	De CHF 2'850 à CHF 3'600	De CHF 12'400 à CHF 15'500	De CHF 148'500 à CHF 186'000	D
H	CHF 3'600 ou plus	CHF 15'500 ou plus	CHF 186'000 ou plus	H

q58

Type: Code

Concept: Household income

Question: Using this card, please tell me which letter describes your household's total income, after tax and compulsory deductions, from all sources? If you don't know the exact figure, please give an estimate

- 1 J
- 2 R
- 3 C
- 4 M
- 5 F
- 6 S
- 7 K
- 8 P
- 9 D
- 10 H
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't Know)

United Kingdom

	Approximate WEEKLY	Approximate MONTHLY	Approximate ANNUAL	
J	Less than £233	Less than £1,014	Less than £12,163	J
R	£233 to under £324	£1,014 to under £1,409	£12,163 to under £16,905	R
C	£324 to under £412	£1,409 to under £1,790	£16,905 to under £21,480	C
M	£412 to under £504	£1,790 to under £2,190	£21,480 to under £26,278	M
F	£504 to under £612	£2,190 to under £2,659	£26,278 to under £31,914	F
S	£612 to under £728	£2,659 to under £3,162	£31,914 to under £37,939	S
K	£728 to under £874	£3,162 to under £3,799	£37,939 to under £45,583	K
P	£874 to under £1,063	£3,799 to under £4,617	£45,583 to under £55,402	P
D	£1,063 to under £1,395	£4,617 to under £6,063	£55,402 to under £72,754	D
H	£1,395 or more	£6,063 or more	£72,754 or more	H

Denmark

Din Husstands samlede NETTOindkomst				
	Tilnærmelsesvis ugentlig	Tilnærmelsesvis månedlig	Tilnærmelsesvis årlig	
J	Mindre end 3.000 kr	Mindre end 13.000 kr	Mindre end 158.000 kr	J
R	Mellem 3.000 og 3.999 kr	Mellem 13.001 og 18.000 kr	Mellem 158.001 og 217.000 kr	R
C	Mellem 4.000 og 4.999 kr	Mellem 18.001 og 23.000 kr	Mellem 217.001 og 273.000 kr	C
M	Mellem 5.000 og 5.999 kr	Mellem 24.001 og 28.000 kr	Mellem 273.001 og 334.000 kr	M
F	Mellem 6.000 og 7.999 kr	Mellem 28.001 og 34.000 kr	Mellem 334.001 og 404.000 kr	F
S	Mellem 8.000 og 8.999 kr	Mellem 34.001 og 40.000 kr	Mellem 404.001 og 477.000 kr	S
K	Mellem 9.000 og 10.999 kr	Mellem 40.001 og 46.000 kr	Mellem 477.001 og 551.000 kr	K
P	Mellem 11.000 og 11.999 kr	Mellem 46.001 og 53.000 kr	Mellem 551.001 og 638.000 kr	P
D	Mellem 12.000 og 14.999 kr	Mellem 53.001 og 65.000 kr	Mellem 638.001 og 776.000 kr	D
H	Over 14.999 kr	Over 65.000 kr	Over 776.000 kr	H

Hungary

	Hozzávetőleges HAVI jövedelem	
J	240 ezer Ft, vagy kevesebb	J
R	240 000 – 299 999 Ft között	R
C	300 000 – 359 999 Ft között	C
M	360 000 – 409 999 Ft között	M
F	410 000 – 459 999 Ft között	F
S	460 000 – 509 999 Ft között	S
K	510 000 – 579 999 Ft között	K
P	580 000 – 659 999 Ft között	P
D	660 000 – 759 999 Ft között	D
H	760 000 Ft felett	H

Spain

	A la semana (aprox.)	Al mes (aprox.)	Al año (aprox.)	
J	180€ o menos	775€ o menos	9300€ o menos	J
R	Entre 181€ y 250€	Entre 776€ y 1100€	Entre 9301€ y 13000€	R
C	Entre 251€ y 325€	Entre 1101€ y 1400€	Entre 13001€ y 17000€	C
M	Entre 326€ y 400€	Entre 1401€ y 1700€	Entre 17001€ y 21000€	M
F	Entre 401€ y 480€	Entre 1701€ y 2000€	Entre 21001€ y 25000€	F
S	Entre 481€ y 550€	Entre 2001€ y 2400€	Entre 25001€ y 29000€	S
K	Entre 551€ y 670€	Entre 2401€ y 2900€	Entre 29001€ y 35000€	K
P	Entre 671€ y 825€	Entre 2901€ y 3500€	Entre 35001€ y 43000€	P
D	Entre 826€ y 1050€	Entre 3501€ y 4500€	Entre 43001€ y 55000€	D
H	Más de 1050€	Más de 4500€	Más de 55000€	H

Germany

	Wöchentlich (ungefähr)	Monatlich (ungefähr)	Jährlich (ungefähr)	
J	bis 260 Euro	bis 1.130 Euro	bis 13.500 Euro	J
R	261 bis 370 Euro	1.131 bis 1.610 Euro	13.501 bis 19.330 Euro	R
C	371 bis 470 Euro	1.611 bis 2.030 Euro	19.331 bis 24.350 Euro	C
M	471 bis 560 Euro	2.031 bis 2.440 Euro	24.351 bis 29.240 Euro	M
F	561 bis 670 Euro	2.441 bis 2.890 Euro	29.241 bis 34.720 Euro	F
S	671 bis 780 Euro	2.891 bis 3.390 Euro	34.721 bis 40.690 Euro	S
K	781 bis 920 Euro	3.391 bis 3.980 Euro	40.691 bis 47.710 Euro	K
P	921 bis 1.100 Euro	3.981 bis 4.750 Euro	47.711 bis 56.940 Euro	P
D	1.101 bis 1.390 Euro	4.751 bis 6.020 Euro	56.941 bis 72.220 Euro	D
H	1.391 Euro oder mehr	6.021 Euro oder mehr	72.221 Euro oder mehr	H

Switzerland

	Approximation HEBDOMADAIRE	Approximation MENSUEL	Approximation ANNUEL	
J	Moins de CHF 750	Moins de CHF 3'300	Moins de CHF 39'500	J
R	De CHF 750 à CHF 1'000	De CHF 3'300 à CHF 4'300	De CHF 39'500 à CHF 52'000	R
C	De CHF 1'000 à CHF 1'250	De CHF 4'300 à CHF 5'400	De CHF 52'000 à CHF 65'000	C
M	De CHF 1'250 à CHF 1'500	De CHF 5'400 à CHF 6'500	De CHF 65'000 à CHF 78'000	M
F	De CHF 1'500 à CHF 1'750	De CHF 6'500 à CHF 7'600	De CHF 78'000 à CHF 91'500	F
S	De CHF 1'750 à CHF 2'050	De CHF 7'600 à CHF 8'900	De CHF 91'500 à CHF 106'000	S
K	De CHF 2'050 à CHF 2'400	De CHF 8'900 à CHF 10'400	De CHF 106'000 à CHF 125'000	K
P	De CHF 2'400 à CHF 2'850	De CHF 10'400 à CHF 12'400	De CHF 125'000 à CHF 148'500	P
D	De CHF 2'850 à CHF 3'600	De CHF 12'400 à CHF 15'500	De CHF 148'500 à CHF 186'000	D
H	CHF 3'600 ou plus	CHF 15'500 ou plus	CHF 186'000 ou plus	H

q59

Type: Code

Concept: Satisfaction income

Question: Which of the descriptions on this card comes closest to how you feel about your household's income nowadays?

- 1 Living comfortably on present income
- 2 Coping on present income
- 3 Finding it difficult on present income
- 4 Finding it very difficult on present income
- 888 (Refusal)
- 999 (Don't Know)

q60

Type: Code

Concept: Self-placement in social scale

Question: In our society, there are groups which tend to be towards the top and groups which tend to be towards the bottom. Below is a scale that runs from the top (10 on the scale) to the bottom (01 on the scale). Where would you put yourself on this scale?

1	01 bottom
2	02
3	03
4	04
5	05
6	06
7	07
8	08
9	09
10	10 top
888	(Refusal)
999	(Don't Know)

5.2 Region codes

Items: qr_uk, q5uk_reg, qr_dk, qr_dk, qr_es, qr_de, qr_ch

United Kingdom

qr_uk

1	North East (England)
2	North West (England)
3	Yorkshire and The Humber
4	East Midlands (England)
5	West Midlands (England)
6	East
7	London
8	South East (England)
9	South West (England)
10	Scotland
11	Wales
12	Northern Ireland

q5uk_reg

1	ENGLAND
2	SCOTLAND

3 WALES

Denmark

qr_dk

- 1 Region Hovedstaden
- 2 Region Sjælland
- 3 Region Syddanmark
- 4 Region Midtjylland
- 5 Region Nordjylland

Hungary

qr_hu

- 1 Budapest
- 2 Pest
- 3 Fejér
- 4 Komárom-Esztergom
- 5 Veszprém
- 6 Győr-Moson-Sopron
- 7 Vas
- 8 Zala
- 9 Baranya
- 10 Somogy
- 11 Tolna
- 12 Borsod-Abaúj-Zemplén
- 13 Heves
- 14 Nógrád
- 15 Hajdú-Bihar
- 16 Jász-Nagykun-Szolnok
- 17 Szabolcs-Szatmár-Bereg
- 18 Bács-Kiskun
- 19 Békés
- 20 Csongrád

Spain

qr_es

- 1 Galicia
- 2 Principado de Asturias
- 3 Cantabria
- 4 País Vasco
- 5 Comunidad Foral de Navarra
- 6 La Rioja
- 7 Aragón
- 8 Comunidad de Madrid
- 9 Castilla y León
- 10 Castilla-La Mancha
- 11 Extremadura
- 12 Cataluña
- 13 Comunidad Valenciana
- 14 Illes Balears
- 15 Andalucía
- 16 Región de Murcia
- 17 Ciudad Autónoma de Ceuta
- 18 Ciudad Autónoma de Melilla
- 19 Canarias

Germany

qr_de

- 1 Baden-Württemberg
- 2 Bayern
- 3 Berlin
- 4 Brandenburg
- 5 Bremen
- 6 Hamburg
- 7 Hessen
- 8 Mecklenburg-Vorpommern
- 9 Niedersachsen
- 10 Nordrhein-Westfalen
- 11 Rheinland-Pfalz

- 12 Saarland
- 13 Sachsen
- 14 Sachsen-Anhalt
- 15 Schleswig-Holstein
- 16 Thüringen

Switzerland

qr_ch

- 1 Genferseeregion (Genf, Waadt, Wallis)
- 2 Espace Mittelland (Bern, Fribourg, Jura, Neuchâtel, Solothurn)
- 3 Nordwestschweiz (Aargau, Basel-Landschaft, Basel-Stadt)
- 4 Zürich
- 5 Ostschweiz (Appenzell A. Rh, Appenzell I. Rh, Glarus, Graubünden, St. Gallen, Schaffhausen, Thurgau)
- 6 Zentralschweiz (Luzern, Nidwalden, Obwalden, Schwyz, Uri, Zug)
- 7 Tessin

5.3 Country-variables

Items: rwpp_gov, rwpp_str, gender_eq_eu, gender_eq_un, women_econ, net_migrationrate, gdp_growth, hdi

rwpp_gov

Type: Code

Concept: Presence of a Right-Wing Populist Party in the coalition government, taking as reference the last national/federal/general elections of each polity.

1. Yes

0. No

rwpp_str

Type: Numeric (decimal)

Concept: Strength of the RWPP in the Parliament

Measurement: seat share (%) calculated over the total number of seats of each parliament (low chamber), taking as reference the last national/federal/general elections of each polity.

gender_eq_eu

Type: Numeric (decimal)

Concept: The Gender Equality Index is a comprehensive measure for monitoring progress in gender equality across the EU over time. The Gender Equality Index gives the EU and the Member States a score from 1 to 100. A score of 100 would mean that a country had reached full equality between women and men.

The variable shows the scores of the 2024 Index (which comes from 2022 data) for Denmark, Germany, Hungary and Spain. The most updated score for UK is from the Gender Equality Index 2020. Data is not available for Switzerland.

Measurement: The Gender Equality Index gives the EU and the Member States a score from 1 to 100. A score of 100 would mean that a country had reached full equality between women and men.

gender_eq_un

Type: Numeric (decimal)

Concept: Gender Inequality Index is a composite metric of gender inequality using three dimensions: reproductive health, empowerment and the labour market. A low GII value indicates low inequality between women and men, and vice-versa. It ranges from 0, where women and men fare equally, to 1.

Measurement: It ranges from 0, where women and men fare equally, to 1, where one gender fares as poorly as possible in all measured dimensions.

women_econ

Type: Numeric (decimal)

Concept: Women Business and Law Index measures how laws and regulations affect women's economic opportunity. Overall scores are calculated by taking the average score of each index (Mobility, Workplace, Pay, Marriage, Parenthood, Entrepreneurship, Assets and Pension).

Measurement: Scale goes from 1 to 100, with 100 representing the highest possible score.

net_migrationrate

Type: Numeric (decimal)

Concept: Net migration is the net total of migrants during the period, that is, the number of immigrants minus the number of emigrants, including both citizens and noncitizens.

Measurement: It is measured in millions of people.

gdp_growth

Type: Numeric (decimal)

Concept: Annual percentage growth rate of GDP at market prices based on constant local currency. GDP is the sum of gross value added by all resident producers in the economy plus any product taxes and minus any subsidies not included in the value of the products

Measurement: Annual percentage growth rate of GDP at market prices based on constant local currency (weighted average). Aggregates are based on constant 2015 prices, expressed in U.S. dollars.

hdi

Type: Numeric (decimal)

Concept: The Human Development Index (HDI) is a summary measure of average achievement in key dimensions of human development: a long and healthy life, being knowledgeable and having a decent standard of living.

Measurement: The HDI is the geometric mean of normalized indices for each of the three dimensions.

Low (< 0.550)

Medium (0.550-0.699)

High (0.700-0.799)

Very high (\geq 0.800)

References

Adhikari, K., Patten, S. B., Patel, A. B., Premji, S., Tough, S., Letourneau, N., Giesbrecht, G., & Metcalfe, A. (2021). Data Harmonization and Data Pooling from Cohort Studies: A Practical Approach for Data Management. *International Journal of Population Data Science*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.23889/IJPDS.V6I1.1680>

Anduiza, E., & Rico, G. (2022). *Sexism and the Far-Right Vote: The Individual Dynamics of Gender Backlash*. <https://doi.org/10.7910/DVN/A11CD5>

Ruiz Jiménez, A. M., Ortiz Barquero, P., & Zambrana Pérez, R. A. (2023.). *Gender differences in voting for Right-Wing Populist Parties*. Madrid: Centro de Estudios Políticos y Constitucionales. Working Paper prepared for the tribute days “Homenaje a José Ramón Montero”.

Spierings, N., & Zaslove, A. (2017). Gender, populist attitudes, and voting: explaining the gender gap in voting for populist radical right and populist radical left parties. *West European Politics*, 40(4), 821–847. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01402382.2017.1287448>